

Local Hidden-Variable Models That Agree with Quantum Mechanics for All Systems

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We prove that there always exists a local hidden-variable (HV) model for all multipartite discrete quantum systems in any states, with mean values of any observable agreeing with those of quantum mechanics (QM), and local measurement functions depending on local detector angles only. We build up to this gradually, starting with a review of Bell's inequality based on his local HV model, which we then show is missing important physical conditions that are actually implied by his model, invalidating his inequality and all conclusions that have been made about the meaning of Bell-inequality violations. Essentially, reports of Bell-inequality violations are the results of putting good data into an inappropriate inequality. We then demonstrate this flaw with an example of a local HV model that agrees with QM for Bell's maximally entangled state, which leads to a Bell-type inequality that can never be violated. We then show that if certain parts of the local HV model are inaccessible to us, we would perceive it as an effectively nonlocal HV model even though the underlying model is local. We then give examples of explicit local HV models agreeing with QM for all multipartite discrete systems. Thus, valid Bell-inequality violations can never actually occur and EPR was correct in principle, whether or not such local processes happen physically. We then suggest possible applications such as hidden-variable computers and hidden-variable teleportation.

I. INTRODUCTION

In 1935, Einstein, Podolsky, and Rosen (EPR) proposed that a necessary requirement for the completeness of any physical theory is that *every element of the physical reality must have a counterpart in the physical theory* [1]. Since quantum mechanics can only give probabilities for measurable quantities but cannot predict *which* value will be measured, EPR concluded that quantum mechanics is incomplete. This suggests that there may be some hidden variable(s) that supplies the necessary information to describe reality completely.

One of the most distinctive features of quantum mechanics are entangled states [2], such as the singlet state

$$|\Psi^-\rangle \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|1^{(A)}\rangle \otimes |2^{(B)}\rangle - |2^{(A)}\rangle \otimes |1^{(B)}\rangle) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ -1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

in a Hilbert space $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}^{(A)} \otimes \mathcal{H}^{(B)}$ where $\mathcal{H}^{(m)}$ is the Hilbert space of subsystem (mode) m , with the convention that the computational basis states of each mode are generically labeled starting on 1 as $\{|1^{(m)}\rangle, \dots, |n_m^{(m)}\rangle\}$, so that the number of levels of mode m is n_m and the total number of levels in \mathcal{H} in an N -mode system is $n \equiv \prod_{m=1}^N n_m = n_1 \cdots n_N$, so $N = 2$ and $n = 4$ in (1).

The nonlocality of states like (1) lies in the fact that measurement of A guarantees that B has the opposite measurement result due to collapse of the wave function no matter how far apart A and B are, and is part of what suggested to EPR that Nature somehow “knows” what the results of each measurement are ahead of time, since otherwise it would take a superluminal signal to coordinate them, and experiments show no information can travel faster than light. This “prearrangement” of measurement results is the essence of a *deterministic* reality; initial conditions determine future results given some equation of motion describing the system's evolution.

However, in 1964, J. S. Bell proposed a simple and persuasive derivation yielding the famous *Bell inequality*, the violation of which by quantum inputs, he argued, proved that no local hidden-variable (HV) theory could be compatible with quantum mechanics (QM) [3]. (Then, by the success of QM in explaining so many otherwise unexplainable physical facts, one could infer that local HV theories are not compatible with physical reality either because they fail to obey the Correspondence Principle for agreeing with a successful physical theory).

In this paper, we show that Bell's derivation is missing crucial information, thereby invalidating his local HV model *prior* to deriving his inequality, effectively *sabotaging* his inequality, so it is actually *not* a requirement of a *valid* local HV model. We then demonstrate this with an explicit example of a *local* HV model for a maximally entangled state. We then show that if certain parts of this local HV model are inaccessible to us, we would *perceive* it as an *effectively nonlocal* HV model despite the underlying local model, and yet we retain the ability to predict measurement results. This effectively nonlocal HV model yields a *different* Bell inequality that can never be violated, and we show that since both the local and effectively nonlocal HV models have inviolable Bell inequalities, EPR has not been disproven. We then explicitly construct *local* HV models for all states of all multipartite systems, all agreeing with QM for mean values but providing the predictive information about measurement results that QM lacks. Contents:

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II. REVIEW OF BELL'S DERIVATION

Here we review the derivation of Bell's inequality (since it is necessary to show how to disprove it), and review his claims on the meaning of violations of his inequality.

A. Derivation of Bell's Inequality

To illustrate his claim, Bell considered two particles A and B in a maximally entangled state such as (1), each passing through a Stern-Gerlach magnet with the orientation of the magnets' fields represented by unit vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} for particles A and B respectively, with measurements taken in units of $\hbar/2$. Since measurement collapses $|\Psi^-\rangle$ onto a system state such that each particle is in the opposite eigenstate of σ_z , Bell examined the average of the product of the two spin components in the directions of the two magnets, which QM defines for a state $|\psi\rangle$ as

$$\langle\sigma_a\sigma_b\rangle\equiv\langle\psi|\sigma_a\sigma_b|\psi\rangle, \quad (2)$$

where the local spin-component operators in the joint space are $\sigma_a\equiv\sigma_a^{(A)}\otimes I^{(B)}$ and $\sigma_b\equiv I^{(A)}\otimes\sigma_b^{(B)}$, where $\sigma_a^{(A)}\equiv\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(A)}\cdot\mathbf{a}$ and $\sigma_b^{(B)}\equiv\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(B)}\cdot\mathbf{b}$, and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(m)}\equiv(\sigma_x^{(m)},\sigma_y^{(m)},\sigma_z^{(m)})$, where $\sigma_k^{(m)}$ are the Pauli spin operators for mode m , so that $\sigma_a\sigma_b=\sigma_a^{(A)}\otimes\sigma_b^{(B)}$.

He then observed that using $|\psi\rangle=|\Psi^-\rangle$ from (1) in (2) yields the quantum-mechanical (and physical) result,

$$\langle\sigma_a\sigma_b\rangle=-\mathbf{a}\cdot\mathbf{b}=-\cos(\theta_{a,b}), \quad (3)$$

where $\theta_{a,b}\equiv\theta_a-\theta_b$ is the relative angle of the detectors, where their absolute angles θ_k are taken with respect to some common reference.

Next, he proposed two "measurement functions" $A(\mathbf{a},\lambda)\in\pm 1$ and $B(\mathbf{b},\lambda)\in\pm 1$ which give the results of the individual measurements of the spin components of particles A and B respectively, determined by some hidden variable λ . He then noted that if $\rho(\lambda)$ is a normalized probability distribution, so that

$$\int\rho(\lambda)d\lambda=1, \quad (4)$$

and $\rho(\lambda)\geq 0\forall\lambda$, then the classical expectation value of the spin-component product is

$$P(\mathbf{a},\mathbf{b})\equiv\int\rho(\lambda)A(\mathbf{a},\lambda)B(\mathbf{b},\lambda)d\lambda. \quad (5)$$

Here he observed that when $\mathbf{a}=\mathbf{b}$, the only way that (5) can equal -1 , as the physical behavior requires, is if

$$B(\mathbf{b},\lambda)=-A(\mathbf{b},\lambda). \quad (6)$$

Pausing to appreciate the meaning of (6), consider Table I, showing simulated measurements on identically prepared systems, where A_M and B_M are measurements of spin results for $\sigma_a^{(A)}$ and $\sigma_b^{(B)}$.

TABLE I: Examples of spin measurements for two relative detector angles, given a spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ system in the singlet state.

IA $\theta_{a,b}=0^\circ$				IB $\theta_{a,b}\approx 53^\circ$			
A_M	B_M	$A_M B_M$	$\langle\sigma_a\sigma_b\rangle$	A_M	B_M	$A_M B_M$	$\langle\sigma_a\sigma_b\rangle$
$(\frac{\hbar}{2})$	$(\frac{\hbar}{2})$	$(\frac{\hbar^2}{4})$	$(\frac{\hbar^2}{4})$	$(\frac{\hbar}{2})$	$(\frac{\hbar}{2})$	$(\frac{\hbar^2}{4})$	$(\frac{\hbar^2}{4})$
+1	-1	-1		-1	-1	+1	
-1	+1	-1		+1	-1	-1	
+1	-1	-1	-1	-1	+1	-1	$-\frac{3}{5}$
+1	-1	-1		+1	-1	-1	
-1	+1	-1		+1	-1	-1	

Table IA shows that when $\mathbf{a}=\mathbf{b}$, $A_M B_M$ is always -1 , but when the detectors are not parallel, as in Table IB, the measured spin components can have the same value, which helps illustrate the physical meaning of (3).

Then, Bell put (6) into (5) to get

$$P(\mathbf{a},\mathbf{b})=-\int\rho(\lambda)A(\mathbf{a},\lambda)A(\mathbf{b},\lambda)d\lambda. \quad (7)$$

If \mathbf{c} is another unit vector, putting it into \mathbf{b} in (7) gives

$$P(\mathbf{a},\mathbf{c})=-\int\rho(\lambda)A(\mathbf{a},\lambda)A(\mathbf{c},\lambda)d\lambda. \quad (8)$$

Next, he took the difference of (7) and (8) as

$$P(\mathbf{a},\mathbf{b})-P(\mathbf{a},\mathbf{c})=-\int\rho(\lambda)[A(\mathbf{a},\lambda)A(\mathbf{b},\lambda)-A(\mathbf{a},\lambda)A(\mathbf{c},\lambda)]d\lambda. \quad (9)$$

Then, since $A(\mathbf{b},\lambda)=\pm 1$, he noted that $A^2(\mathbf{b},\lambda)=1=A(\mathbf{b},\lambda)A(\mathbf{b},\lambda)$, inserted this in the middle of the second term of (9), factored, and took absolute values to get

$$\begin{aligned} P(\mathbf{a},\mathbf{b})-P(\mathbf{a},\mathbf{c}) &= -\int\rho(\lambda)[A(\mathbf{a},\lambda)A(\mathbf{b},\lambda) \\ &\quad -A(\mathbf{a},\lambda)A(\mathbf{b},\lambda)A(\mathbf{b},\lambda)A(\mathbf{c},\lambda)]d\lambda \\ |P(\mathbf{a},\mathbf{b})-P(\mathbf{a},\mathbf{c})| &\leq \int|\rho(\lambda)||A(\mathbf{a},\lambda)A(\mathbf{b},\lambda)| \\ &\quad \times |1-A(\mathbf{b},\lambda)A(\mathbf{c},\lambda)|d\lambda, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where we used the fact that $|\int_{\lambda_0}^{\lambda_1} f(\lambda)d\lambda|\leq\int_{\lambda_0}^{\lambda_1}|f(\lambda)|d\lambda$ if $f(\lambda)$ is Riemann-integrable on $[\lambda_0,\lambda_1]$. Then, since $\rho(\lambda)\geq 0\forall\lambda$, $A(\mathbf{a},\lambda)A(\mathbf{b},\lambda)=\pm 1$, and $1-A(\mathbf{b},\lambda)A(\mathbf{c},\lambda)\in\{0,2\}$, (10) becomes

$$|P(\mathbf{a},\mathbf{b})-P(\mathbf{a},\mathbf{c})|\leq\int\rho(\lambda)d\lambda-\int\rho(\lambda)A(\mathbf{b},\lambda)A(\mathbf{c},\lambda)d\lambda. \quad (11)$$

Then, using (4), and (8) with \mathbf{b} in place of \mathbf{a} as $P(\mathbf{b},\mathbf{c})=-\int\rho(\lambda)A(\mathbf{b},\lambda)A(\mathbf{c},\lambda)d\lambda$, (11) yields *Bell's inequality*,

$$|P(\mathbf{a},\mathbf{b})-P(\mathbf{a},\mathbf{c})|\leq 1+P(\mathbf{b},\mathbf{c}), \quad (12)$$

which Bell claimed must hold true for any local hidden-variable theory of this system [3–6].

As we will soon see, the flaw in Bell's argument actually comes *before* this inequality, rendering it and all related Bell-type inequalities irrelevant, but first we will review its traditional interpretation for context.

B. Violations of Bell's Inequality

To see how Bell's inequality can be violated by quantum results, consider one experiment with \mathbf{a} perpendicular to \mathbf{b} , and another experiment where detector B is rotated to \mathbf{c} , 45° between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} [3, 4]. If the HV mean of (5) could achieve the QM mean of (3) as $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = -\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b} = -\cos(\theta_{a,b})$, then we would get

$$P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = 0, \quad P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) \approx -0.707, \quad P(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}) \approx -0.707, \quad (13)$$

but putting (13) into Bell's inequality in (12) yields a *false statement* as

$$0.707 \leq 0.293, \quad (14)$$

which is a *Bell-inequality violation*. Bell concluded that such violations are proof that local HV theories are incompatible with QM [3], and that therefore $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \neq -\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}$ for local HVs. [To avoid confusion, the false statement in (14) is *not* the reason we claim Bell's inequality to be wrong. However, it *is* a consequence of errors of omission in Bell's model, which we show next in Sec. III.]

The popular interpretation of Bell's result is that *since QM is correct about what it does predict* (and therefore is compatible with physical reality to some extent), *and since local HV theories are incompatible with QM* (since theoretical quantum mean values can violate Bell's inequality), *then one can conclude that local HV models are incompatible with physical reality* (supported by the ability of measurements to violate Bell's inequality).

However, there are fundamental flaws in Bell's derivation that cause Bell's inequality to not truly apply to local HV models, which means that any conclusions drawn by putting either theoretical QM values or real-world data into it have no meaning whatsoever, and therefore the above conclusions about local HV theories are invalid. In other words, the above Bell-inequality violations are not sufficient to invalidate local HV theories.

III. SOME ERRORS IN BELL'S DERIVATION

Here we identify a few errors in Bell's argument, and discuss their implications. Later, in Sec. IV and Sec. V, we will see additional features missing from his model.

A. Missing Physical Conditions in Bell's Model

If the Bell inequality in (12) truly applies to this system, then the local HV model upon which it is based needs to include *all* relevant facts. Equation (6), $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) = -A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$, is one such fact, but it is not enough! To see *part* of what Bell's derivation is missing, consider that the quantum-mechanical (and physical) facts

$$\langle \sigma_a \rangle = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \langle \sigma_b \rangle = 0 \quad (15)$$

yield *two more constraints*, on equal footing with (6);

$$\int \rho(\lambda) A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) d\lambda = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \int \rho(\lambda) B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) d\lambda = 0. \quad (16)$$

Note that (16) is not a set of newly imposed constraints; it is a consequence of defining A , B , and ρ and is intrinsically implied by Bell's model.

Now, since $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ and $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ can only be ± 1 , they must be *piecewise* over λ . There may be many pieces, but to satisfy (16), there must be *two types of regions* for each function, one for each spin. To see why, suppose that only one *value* of $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ occurs over all λ , call this value $A_- \equiv -1$. Then (16) would yield $0 = \int \rho(\lambda) A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) d\lambda = A_- \int \rho(\lambda) d\lambda = A_- = 0$, directly conflicting with the requirement that $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) = \pm 1$. To see why *two-region* functions *do* satisfy (16), let the *two possible values* of $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ be $A_\pm \equiv \pm 1$, and suppose there is some large piecewise definition of q pieces such as

$$A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) = \begin{cases} A_1(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) \equiv A_+; & \lambda \in [\lambda_0, \lambda_1) \\ A_2(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) \equiv A_-; & \lambda \in [\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \\ A_3(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) \equiv A_+; & \lambda \in [\lambda_2, \lambda_3) \\ \vdots \\ A_q(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) \equiv A_-; & \lambda \in [\lambda_{q-1}, \lambda_q], \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

where $A_k(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ is the measurement function for the value in the k th piece, and the specific values (A_+ or A_-) for each $A_k(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ shown in (17) are just for example here. Then putting (17) into (16) gives

$$\int_{\lambda_0}^{\lambda_1} \rho(\lambda) A_1(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) d\lambda + \cdots + \int_{\lambda_{q-1}}^{\lambda_q} \rho(\lambda) A_q(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) d\lambda = 0. \quad (18)$$

[In general, $\rho(\lambda)$ may also have a piecewise definition, but it does not affect anything here to write it in general form]. Now, since there is always at least one piece with each type of value (since both must occur), we can group all the terms of each type together in (18) as

$$\left(\sum_j \int_{\lambda_j^{\{l+\}} }^{\lambda_j^{\{u+\}} } \rho(\lambda) A_+ d\lambda \right) + \left(\sum_h \int_{\lambda_h^{\{l-\}} }^{\lambda_h^{\{u-\}} } \rho(\lambda) A_- d\lambda \right) = 0, \quad (19)$$

where $\{\lambda_j^{\{u+\}}\}, \{\lambda_j^{\{l+\}}\}$ are the ordered sets of all upper and lower points of λ that bound regions containing A_+ , and $\{\lambda_h^{\{u-\}}\}, \{\lambda_h^{\{l-\}}\}$ are the ordered sets containing A_- (note that these sets can share *endpoints*, but every *interval* constituting a piece only falls into one of the two groups). Then, since the *values* A_\pm are independent of λ [keeping in mind that they are *determined* by \mathbf{a} and λ as seen in (17) which has already been applied in (19)], these values come out of the sign-grouped integrals as

$$A_+ \int_+ \rho(\lambda) d\lambda + A_- \int_- \rho(\lambda) d\lambda = 0 \quad (20)$$

$$\int_+ \rho(\lambda) d\lambda - \int_- \rho(\lambda) d\lambda = 0,$$

where $\int_+ \rho(\lambda) d\lambda \equiv \sum_j \int_{\lambda_j^{\{l+\}} }^{\lambda_j^{\{u+\}} } \rho(\lambda) d\lambda$ and $\int_- \rho(\lambda) d\lambda \equiv \sum_h \int_{\lambda_h^{\{l-\}} }^{\lambda_h^{\{u-\}} } \rho(\lambda) d\lambda$. Then, since these two pieces are mutually exclusive, $\int \rho(\lambda) d\lambda = 1$ from (4) becomes

$$\int_+ \rho(\lambda) d\lambda + \int_- \rho(\lambda) d\lambda = 1. \quad (21)$$

Then, solving (20) and (21) yields

$$\int_+ \rho(\lambda) d\lambda = \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad \int_- \rho(\lambda) d\lambda = \frac{1}{2}. \quad (22)$$

However, the key result here is that $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ requires *two* net regions, which will affect $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ as we show next.

B. Updating Bell's Model

Now, although Bell's argument already takes the physical fact of anticorrelation into account with $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) = -A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ from (6), it also needs to take into account the physical facts of lone spin-component averages from (16).

Therefore, in the spin-component product average from (7), the different vector arguments in the product of $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ mean that *four* possible domains need to be considered in the general problem; one for each fixed-sign combination of this product. In other words, similar to what we did in (17–20), we reorganize the problem into four groups in which the *values* of $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ and $A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ are *constant* in each group as $\{A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda), A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)\} \in \{\{+1, +1\}, \{+1, -1\}, \{-1, +1\}, \{-1, -1\}\}$. Implementing this in (7) yields

$$\begin{aligned} P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) &= -\int \rho(\lambda)A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)d\lambda \\ &= -\left[\int_{++} \rho(\lambda)A_+A_+d\lambda + \int_{+-} \rho(\lambda)A_+A_-d\lambda \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int_{-+} \rho(\lambda)A_-A_+d\lambda + \int_{--} \rho(\lambda)A_-A_-d\lambda \right] \\ &= -\left[A_+A_+\int_{++} \rho(\lambda)d\lambda + A_+A_-\int_{+-} \rho(\lambda)d\lambda \right. \\ &\quad \left. + A_-A_+\int_{-+} \rho(\lambda)d\lambda + A_-A_-\int_{--} \rho(\lambda)d\lambda \right] \quad (23) \\ &= -\left[\int_{++} \rho(\lambda)d\lambda - \int_{+-} \rho(\lambda)d\lambda \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \int_{-+} \rho(\lambda)d\lambda + \int_{--} \rho(\lambda)d\lambda \right] \\ P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) &= -p_{++} + p_{+-} + p_{-+} - p_{--}, \end{aligned}$$

where $p_{jk} \equiv \int_{jk} \rho(\lambda)d\lambda$ for $j, k \in \{+, -\}$.

Therefore, these four regions and these four physical requirements (normalization, spin-component product average, and both lone spin component averages) taken together yield an *invertible* system of equations as

$$\begin{aligned} p_{++} + p_{+-} + p_{-+} + p_{--} &= 1 \\ -p_{++} + p_{+-} + p_{-+} - p_{--} &= -c_{\theta_{a,b}} \quad (24) \\ p_{++} + p_{+-} - p_{-+} - p_{--} &= 0 \\ p_{++} - p_{+-} + p_{-+} - p_{--} &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

where hereafter we use $c_\theta \equiv \cos(\theta)$ and $s_\theta \equiv \sin(\theta)$, and we put $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = -c_{\theta_{a,b}}$ into (23) to get (24) since it is a physical requirement for a successful model *and* because *the invertibility of (24) indicates that it can indeed be satisfied*. This yields the matrix equation

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & 1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} p_{++} \\ p_{+-} \\ p_{-+} \\ p_{--} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -c_{\theta_{a,b}} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (25)$$

the solution of which is

$$\begin{aligned} p_{++} &= \frac{1}{4}(1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ p_{+-} &= \frac{1}{4}(1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ p_{-+} &= \frac{1}{4}(1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ p_{--} &= \frac{1}{4}(1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}}), \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

which, when plugged into (23) yields

$$\begin{aligned} P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) &= \frac{1}{4}(-1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}} + 1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}} + 1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}} - 1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ &= -c_{\theta_{a,b}}, \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

which means that this HV model itself actually gives the correct quantum result exactly. *In other words, when the*

lone spin-component means are taken into account, the quantity $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = -\int \rho(\lambda)A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)d\lambda$ from (7) is $-c_{\theta_{a,b}}$ already! That is, the HV model's statistical expression of $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ is in exact agreement with QM (and experiment) before we even start to derive an inequality.

Note that the appearance of $c_{\theta_{a,b}}$ in the probabilities in (26) *seems* to make this a *nonlocal* HV model. However, as will show with an example in Sec. IV, this nonlocality may be just an illusion; it is the model we *perceive* if we ignore certain parts of an underlying *locally real* HV model, meaning that (26) can be viewed as being merely an *effectively* nonlocal model due to observer ignorance.

Thus, as we will prove in Sec. V, the tightest valid “inequality” Bell could have gotten should have been

$$|P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| = |-c_{\theta_{a,b}} + c_{\theta_{a,c}}| = |\mathbf{a} \cdot (\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{c})|, \quad (28)$$

which is *always true* and cannot be violated. Yet, since his probabilities would have been nonlocal, this would seem to be a dead end. However, Sec. IV shows that this model can still be local at its core, vindicating local HVs.

So where did Bell go wrong? While Sec. IV will disprove his results by example, here we see his simple oversight that led to two subtle errors. By not including the lone spin-component averages of (16) as necessary conditions in his model, he did not obtain the solvable set of equations in (24) that such a physical system must obey. Thus, his model lacked the reorganization into four net regions that permits the measurement functions to take on *constant values* in those regions and *come out of the integrals*, which makes *irrelevant* all of the steps of his derivation after (9). However, *more importantly*, as we show in Sec. V, *what Bell was really missing is the classical spin-component magnitudes*, which Sec. IV shows how to include in ways compatible with QM *and* locality.

Thus, if Bell had used a *more complete* model of the system by including (16), he would not have derived his inequality, but instead would have arrived at (28) but would have likely *still* concluded that local HV theories are impossible since he would have noted that the probabilities of (26) are “nonlocal” so he would have still claimed his same result but there would be no inequality to test; the nonlocal PDF would be his focus instead.

Thus Bell's inequality does not apply to local HV models because it is derived from an incomplete picture of an effectively *nonlocal* HV model [as seen in (26)], where the missing information of lone spin-component averages and spin-component magnitudes *sabotages* the model.

It might seem that somehow using $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) = -A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ is what made this model appear “nonlocal,” however, even if we do *not* use that and instead keep $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ in the problem, it *still* breaks into four regions, and the only difference at the end is that the signs in front of $c_{\theta_{a,b}}$ in (26) are opposite of what they are there.

As we now show in Sec. IV A, *all apparent nonlocality of this system disappears if we consider a fully classical model from the start*, and even the apparent nonlocality of $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) = -A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ can be seen to be fully compatible with locality, and we include quantization in Sec. IV B.

IV. A WORKING LOCAL HIDDEN-VARIABLE MODEL

Here we achieve something significant; a fully classical local hidden-variable model that agrees with the results of quantum mechanics for a maximally entangled state.

We will not model spin exactly, but rather something that *indicates* spin; nevertheless, the result is a product of local functions whose average agrees with QM, something Bell claimed to be mathematically impossible.

Note that this entire local HV model is just a demonstration that such a thing is possible *in principle*, and does not necessarily describe reality. Just because we find *an* explanation does not mean we have found *the* explanation. Our goal here is simply to show that such a thing is *possible*. Therefore, the following “explanation” is merely a conceptual motivation.

A. A Local Hidden-Variable Model that Agrees with QM for a Maximally Entangled State

The idea here is simple: to examine the ability of a classical theory to model the reality described by QM, *we need to start with a fully classical theory*.

Beyond just omitting the lone spin-component averages, Bell’s insistence that $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) = \pm 1$ and $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) = \pm 1$ from the start, although consistent with observation, also helped to implicitly infect his model with nonlocality, which we will show in Sec. IV C. But as we will see, we can *still obtain* $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) = \pm 1$ and $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) = \pm 1$ and even $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) = -A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ as *byproducts of a local HV theory, as long as we keep the theory intrinsically classical by not insisting upon these requirements at first*.

To construct our fully classical model, we specify the following features:

1. The two particles A and B start out as “locked” rotating together before they fly apart.
2. The axis of spin is parallel to the direction of the particles’ paths as they fly away from each other.
3. Their spin rotations point in the same direction initially and at all times later, but one of them has a π phase shift from the other, meaning its “prime meridian” about the axis of rotation is on the opposite side as the “prime meridian” of the other particle about that same axis. (These first three steps will look different depending on different initial configurations, and as we will see soon, this is related to the perceived quantum state that applies to the system.)
4. Each particle has some classically identifiable “geography” so that even if they were spheres, their rotation could still be observed in principle as if a grid were painted on them (whether that could be practically observed or not). As to the plausibility of this, consider a circularly polarized photon whose spin is parallel with its direction of motion, and yet has an electric field vector perpendicular to this motion, which rotates in the plane perpendicular to its motion.

5. The two detectors D_A and D_B that intercept each particle include “polarizing unit vectors” \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} in the plane perpendicular to the paths of A and B .
6. Within each particle, the radius vector along the equator of rotation from its center to its “prime meridian” is the vector representing the “progress” of the particle in its rotation cycle at any time, which we call its *prime rotation vector* \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} . (This vector is not necessarily part of the particle itself, but rather is just way to keep track of its rotation classically.) In the case of a circularly polarized photon, the electric field vector could act as this prime rotation vector.
7. The detector then only “sees” a projected component of the prime rotation vector, and this component is changing in time. The value of this component (magnitude and sign) at the projecting filter is what we will call its *classical measurement function*. (We will see later that the two-valued sign of this component is its *quantum measurement function*, and we offer a simple explanation for the quantization in Sec. IV B.)
8. To get a classical statistical framework for this model, we suppose at first that neither the frequency of rotation nor the initial conditions are known to the experimenters, and therefore that measurements at each detector are done at arbitrary times in the period of rotation (but that each pair of measurements, one at each detector, are done simultaneously). The “hidden” variable of integration is then *time*, and it has a uniform probability density, so our expectation values are *time averages* (see Sec. VII for more about time).

Figure 1 shows all of the above features schematically.

FIG. 1: (color online) (a) Particles A and B , initially joined and rotating together with a π phase shift, fly apart toward detectors D_A and D_B . (b) Prime rotation vectors \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} of A and B with phase angles $\phi_A(t)$ and $\phi_B(t)$ compared to detector vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} (not to scale) with detector angles θ_a and θ_b . Relative angles $\alpha(t) \equiv \phi_A(t) - \theta_a$ and $\beta(t) \equiv \phi_B(t) - \theta_b$ determine the time-dependent scalar projections of \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} onto their own detector vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} .

Now we build the model *mathematically*, based on Fig. 1 and the features described above. The angles of the prime rotation vectors of the two particles in the azimuthal plane are

$$\begin{aligned}\phi_A(t) &= \omega t + \phi_0 \\ \phi_B(t) &= \omega t + \phi_0 + \pi; \quad \omega \equiv \frac{2\pi}{T},\end{aligned}\quad (29)$$

where T is the rotation period and we take time t to start at 0[s], and initial conditions are $\phi_A(0) \equiv \phi_0$ and $\phi_B(0) = \phi_0 + \pi$. The angles between each particle's prime rotation vector and its detector vector are then

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha(\mathbf{a}, t) &\equiv \phi_A(t) - \theta_a = \omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a \\ \beta(\mathbf{b}, t) &\equiv \phi_B(t) - \theta_b = \omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b.\end{aligned}\quad (30)$$

If what we call the *classical spin component in the direction of each detector* is $\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{A}$ and $\mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{B}$, then these are

$$\begin{aligned}|\mathbf{A}| \cos[\alpha(\mathbf{a}, t)] &= |\mathbf{A}| \cos(\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a) = |\mathbf{A}| c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a} \\ |\mathbf{B}| \cos[\beta(\mathbf{b}, t)] &= |\mathbf{B}| \cos(\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b) = |\mathbf{B}| c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b}.\end{aligned}\quad (31)$$

Now consider the following product of these classical spin components supposing that $|\mathbf{A}| = |\mathbf{B}| \equiv \sqrt{2}$ as

$$\begin{aligned}&|\mathbf{A}| c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a} |\mathbf{B}| c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b} \\ &= 2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0} c_{\theta_a} + s_{\omega t + \phi_0} s_{\theta_a})(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi} c_{\theta_b} + s_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi} s_{\theta_b}) \\ &= -2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0} c_{\theta_a} + s_{\omega t + \phi_0} s_{\theta_a})(c_{\omega t + \phi_0} c_{\theta_b} + s_{\omega t + \phi_0} s_{\theta_b}) \\ &= -2[c_{\omega t + \phi_0}^2 c_{\theta_a} c_{\theta_b} + s_{\omega t + \phi_0}^2 c_{\omega t + \phi_0} (c_{\theta_a} s_{\theta_b} + s_{\theta_a} c_{\theta_b}) \\ &\quad + s_{\omega t + \phi_0}^2 s_{\theta_a} s_{\theta_b}] \\ &= -2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0}^2 c_{\theta_a} c_{\theta_b} + \frac{1}{2} s_{2[\omega t + \phi_0]} s_{\theta_a + \theta_b} + s_{\omega t + \phi_0}^2 s_{\theta_a} s_{\theta_b}).\end{aligned}\quad (32)$$

Then, notice here that the time average will get rid of the middle term, while preserving the end terms;

$$\begin{aligned}&\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T |\mathbf{A}| c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a} |\mathbf{B}| c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b} dt \\ &= -2(c_{\theta_a} c_{\theta_b} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T c_{\omega t + \phi_0}^2 dt + s_{\theta_a + \theta_b} \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T s_{2[\omega t + \phi_0]} dt \\ &\quad + s_{\theta_a} s_{\theta_b} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T s_{\omega t + \phi_0}^2 dt) \\ &= -2(c_{\theta_a} c_{\theta_b} \frac{1}{2} + 0 + s_{\theta_a} s_{\theta_b} \frac{1}{2}) = -(c_{\theta_a} c_{\theta_b} + s_{\theta_a} s_{\theta_b}) \\ &= -c_{\theta_a - \theta_b} \\ &= -c_{\theta_{a,b}},\end{aligned}\quad (33)$$

which is exactly the result we want, and we got it from a *classical local model*, where we used the well-known fact that for time-harmonic functions $f(t)$ of fundamental period T , the time average over time window $\tau \gg T$ obeys $\frac{1}{\tau} \int_0^\tau f(t) dt \approx \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T f(t) dt$ [7]. Thus, the time average “washed out” the extra term that would have made this a separable product of independent variables, leaving a mathematically *inseparable* function of the detector angles in its wake. [If each prepared pair has a different random ϕ_0 , (33) shows that we can average over those and get this same result (also confirmed numerically).]

In this model, the *classical measurement functions* are just the classical spin components;

$$\begin{aligned}A_C(\mathbf{a}, t) &\equiv |\mathbf{A}| \cos[\alpha(\mathbf{a}, t)] = \sqrt{2} c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a} \\ B_C(\mathbf{b}, t) &\equiv |\mathbf{B}| \cos[\beta(\mathbf{b}, t)] = \sqrt{2} c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b}.\end{aligned}\quad (34)$$

Notice that since t is an independent variable here, and both of these functions only depend on their *own* detector

vector, these are truly *local* functions. Furthermore, they are fully *real* meaning that the entire spin component exists at all times without ambiguity. Moreover, they are *deterministic*, meaning that if we know T and the initial condition ϕ_0 , we can predict the future spin-component values at all times t .

The classical probability distribution function (PDF) is that of a *uniform* distribution because the “hidden” variable is time t , so

$$\rho_C(t) = \frac{1}{T}; \quad t \in [0, T], \quad (35)$$

where again, this is for the simplified time average, as explained after (33), since its results match those of the true time average for time window $\tau \gg T$ and $t \in [-\infty, +\infty]$.

Thus, our fully classical system satisfies normalization, spin-component product average, and lone spin-component average relations as

$$\begin{aligned}\int_0^T \rho_C(t) dt &= 1 \\ \int_0^T \rho_C(t) A_C(\mathbf{a}, t) B_C(\mathbf{b}, t) dt &= -c_{\theta_{a,b}} \\ \int_0^T \rho_C(t) A_C(\mathbf{a}, t) dt &= 0 \\ \int_0^T \rho_C(t) B_C(\mathbf{b}, t) dt &= 0,\end{aligned}\quad (36)$$

where line 1 of (36) follows from (35), line 2 follows from (33) using (34) and (35), and lines 3 and 4 follow from (34) and (35). Figure 2 shows the spin-component product average in line 2 of (36) for simulated data, illustrating the success of this classical local HV model in agreeing with the quantum-mechanical prediction (and also measured mean values of this physical system).

FIG. 2: (color online) Simulation of time-based measurements to get the spin-component product average for our local HV model. Keeping $\theta_b = 0$, 1000 trials were done at each of 80 equally-spaced values of θ_a , to yield 80 values of $\theta_{a,b} \equiv \theta_a - \theta_b$ with $\phi_0 = 0$. At each value of $\theta_{a,b}$, for each of its 1000 trials, a random value of t is produced between 0 and T (where $T = 1$ in the simulation), and that value of t was then used to compute $A_C(\mathbf{a}, t) B_C(\mathbf{b}, t)$ using (34). Then the average value of $A_C(\mathbf{a}, t) B_C(\mathbf{b}, t)$ over all trials for a particular $\theta_{a,b}$ was computed and plotted as an experimental estimator for $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ at that $\theta_{a,b}$. See Sec. IV B for an explanation of how spin quantization might be naturally included in this model.

Furthermore, the local HV classical measurement functions naturally obey the lone spin-component averages in lines 3 and 4 of (36), *and* they obey the anticorrelation relation when detector vectors align as $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{b}$;

$$\begin{aligned} A_C(\mathbf{b}, t) &= \sqrt{2}c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_b} \\ B_C(\mathbf{b}, t) &= \sqrt{2}c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b} = -\sqrt{2}c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_b} = -A_C(\mathbf{b}, t), \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

which is like $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) = -A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ of (6), but here, the *illusion* of “nonlocality” comes from the correlation arising from the fact that both spins are initially locked together rotating at the same frequency – a truly classical origin for the correlation, with no “spooky action at a distance” necessary to maintain that correlation into the future.

In fact, the only thing this model does not seem to do *directly* is achieve the physical requirement of producing the quantized spin values of ± 1 , *except that it actually does, if we look carefully*. Notice that we can always rewrite the classical measurement functions as

$$\begin{aligned} A_C(\mathbf{a}, t) &= \sqrt{2}|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a}| \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a}) \\ B_C(\mathbf{b}, t) &= \sqrt{2}|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b}| \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b}), \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

where we define the two-valued sign as

$$\text{sgn}_2(x) \equiv \text{sgn}(x) + \delta_{x,0} = \begin{cases} +1; & x \geq 0 \\ -1; & x < 0, \end{cases} \quad (39)$$

which is valid in (38) because when the cosine is 0, the *magnitude* will be 0 and therefore the sign function does not need to be 0 to make the whole quantity 0. Thus, the classical measurement functions can be written in terms of the *quantum* measurement functions (with time as the hidden variable) as

$$\begin{aligned} A_C(\mathbf{a}, t) &= \sqrt{2}|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a}| A(\mathbf{a}, t) \\ B_C(\mathbf{b}, t) &= \sqrt{2}|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b}| B(\mathbf{b}, t), \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

where the *quantum measurement functions* are

$$\begin{aligned} A(\mathbf{a}, t) &\equiv \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a}) \in \{-1, +1\} \\ B(\mathbf{b}, t) &\equiv \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b}) \in \{-1, +1\}, \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

which obey $B(\mathbf{b}, t) = -A(\mathbf{b}, t)$ at any time.

Thus, this classical local HV model *does* contain the properly quantized quantum measurement functions hiding in plain sight. Furthermore, it gives us their *explicit time-dependence*, meaning that if we know the initial condition ϕ_0 and T , *we can predict the exact results of each quantum spin measurement at all later times*.

So the quantized measurement functions are part of the classical model already, and as Sec. IV C will show, our loss of knowledge of the *magnitudes* of the spin components will induce the same effectively nonlocal HV model that Bell should have gotten had he included lone spin-component averages.

But why is our knowledge of the spin-component magnitudes missing in the first place? And where does that $\sqrt{2}$ come from? Section IV B offers some simple possible answers to these questions.

B. Possible Explanation for Quantized Measurement Functions and Our Inability to Know Spin-Component Magnitudes

Here we give a plausible explanation for why we do not have access to the actual spin component, while still allowing for it to exist. This mechanism explains how the *quantum* measurement functions become the only observables, and sets the stage for Section IV C which shows that the loss of this information leads to the effectively nonlocal HV model as what we perceive. (As with all of this, the plausibility of such a thing does not mean it is *true*, but rather that it is at least one conceivable hypothetical explanation that permits a local HV model.)

We start with the following suppositions:

1. Suppose that the two particles of Sec. IV A are circularly polarized photons, and that *prior* to the polarizers, *the full spin components do exist*.
2. Next, we accept the physical fact that, for whatever reason, *a photon is only absorbed or emitted in discrete packets*, so that photons of energy lower than $\hbar\omega$ are never created.
3. Despite Supposition 2, we suppose that the electric and magnetic fields of the photon are fully classical.
4. Then, for a single photon, *the act of absorptive polarization* as it encounters the polarizer is an *all-or-nothing* event, so *either the whole photon gets absorbed, or the whole photon passes, regardless of detector angle*. (We do not need to worry about the *mechanism* of this all-or-nothing absorption here; it is just a fact to take into account in the present model.)
5. This all-or-nothing interaction of the photon with the polarizer means that the cosine-squared factor that would act as a damping factor in a macroscopic classical beam intensity (by Malus’s Law) will act as a *probability* to indicate *the chance that a single photon will pass*, which in this context, is *purely classical*.
6. Any total absorptions lead to noncoincidence events, so they are not part of the experiment, and are thus postselected away. Therefore the transmission probability $|c_\alpha|^2$ does not affect our results either, also due to postselection and renormalization. Instead, we model the transmission case as splitting into two types; one in which the polarizer absorbs and then emits the photon with its same original phase with probability $|c_\alpha|$ (*not squared*), and another type that absorbs and then emits each photon with a different random phase shift, with probability $1 - |c_\alpha|$. These probabilities are *conditional* given that transmission has happened, and are also classical.
7. Suppose the *direction* of the linearly projected electric field \mathbf{E}' determines which type of measurement happens; if \mathbf{E}' points *up* in the polarizer’s direction, it will cause an *H*-polarized detection, and if \mathbf{E}' points *down* in the polarizer’s direction, it will cause a *V*-polarized detection. Thus, in this model, detections are really

indirect measurements of projected field direction, and this is conceptually consistent with the nonsquared two-type transmission probabilities of Supposition 6.

Then, recall that the electric field of a monochromatic plane wave moving in the $\pm z$ direction is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E} &\equiv \begin{pmatrix} E_x \\ E_y \\ E_z \end{pmatrix} = \text{Re} \left[\begin{pmatrix} E_{x,0} e^{i\phi_x} \\ E_{y,0} e^{i\phi_y} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} e^{i(\pm kz - \omega t)} \right] \\ &= \text{Re} \left[|\tilde{\mathbf{E}}| \begin{pmatrix} \hat{E}_x \\ \hat{E}_y \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} e^{i(\pm kz - \omega t)} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

where $k \equiv \frac{2\pi}{cT}$, where c is the speed of light, $E_{x,0} \geq 0$, and $E_{y,0} \geq 0$, where its classical Jones vector is

$$\hat{\mathbf{E}} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \hat{E}_x \\ \hat{E}_y \end{pmatrix} \equiv \frac{1}{|\tilde{\mathbf{E}}|} \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{E}_x \\ \tilde{E}_y \end{pmatrix} = e^{i\phi_x} \begin{pmatrix} c_\varphi \\ s_\varphi e^{i(\phi_y - \phi_x)} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (43)$$

with field phasors $\tilde{E}_x \equiv E_{x,0} e^{i\phi_x}$ and $\tilde{E}_y \equiv E_{y,0} e^{i\phi_y}$, and where $c_\varphi = \frac{E_{x,0}}{|\tilde{\mathbf{E}}|}$ and $s_\varphi = \frac{E_{y,0}}{|\tilde{\mathbf{E}}|}$ with $\varphi \equiv \text{atan}(\frac{E_{y,0}}{E_{x,0}})$. For circularly polarized photons, $\phi_y - \phi_x = \pm \frac{\pi}{2}$ and $E_{x,0} = E_{y,0}$, so $|\mathbf{E}| = \sqrt{E_{x,0}^2 + E_{y,0}^2} = \sqrt{2} E_{x,0}$ and (43) becomes

$$\hat{\mathbf{E}} = \frac{e^{i\phi_x}}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \pm i \end{pmatrix} \equiv \hat{\mathbf{E}}_L, \quad (44)$$

so by (42), $|\mathbf{E}| = E_{x,0} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} |\tilde{\mathbf{E}}|$, and we define handedness intrinsically by pointing the right-hand thumb in a photon's propagation direction, and if the electric field at a fixed axial position rotates over time in the direction that the right-hand fingers point, we call that *R-handed*. Thus, if the field rotates in the positive azimuthal direction, the photon propagating in the $+z$ direction is *R-handed* and corresponds to the upper-sign case in (44).

A linear polarizer at angle θ_c above the $+x$ direction is modeled in Jones calculus as the projector of $(\begin{smallmatrix} c_{\theta_c} \\ s_{\theta_c} \end{smallmatrix})$ as

$$P_{H(\theta_c)} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} c_{\theta_c}^2 & c_{\theta_c} s_{\theta_c} \\ s_{\theta_c} c_{\theta_c} & s_{\theta_c}^2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (45)$$

Then applying $P_{H(\theta_c)}$ to a circularly polarized field gives

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{E}}' &\equiv P_{H(\theta_c)} \hat{\mathbf{E}}_L = \begin{pmatrix} c_{\theta_c}^2 & c_{\theta_c} s_{\theta_c} \\ s_{\theta_c} c_{\theta_c} & s_{\theta_c}^2 \end{pmatrix} \frac{e^{i\phi_x}}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \pm i \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \frac{e^{i\phi_x}}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} c_{\theta_c} (c_{\theta_c} \pm i s_{\theta_c}) \\ s_{\theta_c} (c_{\theta_c} \pm i s_{\theta_c}) \end{pmatrix} = \frac{e^{i\phi_x} e^{\pm i\theta_c}}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} c_{\theta_c} \\ s_{\theta_c} \end{pmatrix}, \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

where we leave this unnormalized since we must retain its magnitude anyway to uphold the circular-linear Malus's law at the end. Since both photons physically rotate in the same direction, if we treat the *L*-handed particle as an *R*-handed particle moving in the $-z$ direction, then both versions get $+\theta_c$, and converting to real fields gives

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} E'_x \\ E'_y \end{pmatrix} &= \text{Re} [|\tilde{\mathbf{E}}| \tilde{\mathbf{E}}' e^{i(\pm kz - \omega t)}] \\ &= \frac{|\tilde{\mathbf{E}}|}{\sqrt{2}} \text{Re} \left[e^{i(\phi_x + \theta_c \pm kz - \omega t)} \begin{pmatrix} c_{\theta_c} \\ s_{\theta_c} \end{pmatrix} \right] \\ &= |\mathbf{E}| c_{\phi_x + \theta_c \pm kz - \omega t} \begin{pmatrix} c_{\theta_c} \\ s_{\theta_c} \end{pmatrix} = |\mathbf{E}| c_{\omega t \mp kz - \phi_x - \theta_c} \begin{pmatrix} c_{\theta_c} \\ s_{\theta_c} \end{pmatrix} \\ &\equiv |\mathbf{E}| c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c} \mathbf{c}, \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

where $\mathbf{c} \equiv c_{\theta_c} \hat{\mathbf{x}} + s_{\theta_c} \hat{\mathbf{y}}$ is the unit vector in the direction of the polarizer's vector in terms of its angle θ_c above $+\hat{\mathbf{x}}$, and if both particles start at $z = 0$, with both detectors a distance d from that point, then their axial positions at each detector are $z_A = +d$ and $z_B = -d$, so then $\mp kz - \phi_x = -kd - \phi_x \equiv \phi_0$ for both. Note that $|\tilde{\mathbf{E}}|$ is included in (47) because in (42) it plays a similar role to $e^{i(\pm kz - \omega t)}$ in calculating the real field from its phasor and thus (47) obeys Malus's law for circular light into a linear polarizer which is $\langle |\mathbf{E}'|^2 \rangle = \frac{1}{2} |\mathbf{E}|^2$ by time averaging.

(Alternatively, instead of an absorptive polarizer, we could use a [unitary] polarizing beam splitter [PBS] and two detectors, but the detectors would then provide the projective absorptive loss.)

The factor of $c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}$ describes Malus's law's *instantaneous* effect on the electric field. Furthermore, notice that $c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}$ contains *sign* information which, if grouped with unit vector \mathbf{c} , indicates the direction of the electric field as it exits the polarizer, so then from (47),

$$\mathbf{E}' = |\mathbf{E}| c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c} |\text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}) \mathbf{c} \equiv |\mathbf{E}| c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c} \mathbf{c}' \quad (48)$$

where the electric field's unit vector is then

$$\mathbf{c}' \equiv \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}) \mathbf{c}, \quad (49)$$

and again sgn_2 is the special two-valued sign function from (39), valid because the magnitude part $|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}|$ makes (48) zero when it needs to be.

Here, we take into account the all-or-nothing behavior of single-photon absorption by the polarizer without losing the classicality of our model. First, note that when $\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c = m\pi$; $m \in 0, \pm 1, \dots$, the photon definitely passes (because \mathbf{E} aligns with the polarizer slit), so its entire energy of $\hbar\omega$ is preserved. Since energy is proportional to $|\mathbf{E}|^2$, the fact that the whole photon energy is passed means that *the electric field of passed photons is the same as that of entering photons* (up to a possible phase shift). Thus, *for a single photon exiting the polarizer*, its electric field when $\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c = m\pi$ must be

$$\mathbf{E}'_\gamma \equiv \mathbf{E}' = |\mathbf{E}| \mathbf{c}', \quad (50)$$

so the *magnitude* of a single passed photon's electric field must be $|\mathbf{E}|$, the same as its input magnitude.

Therefore, *at any value of $\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c$, any passed photons must also have electric field magnitude $|\mathbf{E}|$* . Then, since by Suppositions 5 and 6, $|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}|^2$ only enters the problem as a transmission probability which is discarded due to coincidence postselection, and since $|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}|$ is merely the *conditional* transmission probability for in-phase re-emissions, and $1 - |c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}|$ is the *conditional* transmission probability for *random-phase* re-emissions, then *those factors cannot affect the actual magnitude of the photon's electric field, itself*.

To keep the photon locally real and to account for the change in photon polarization physically, we now suppose that the polarizer has some finite thickness which is *at least thick enough for \mathbf{E} to rotate a full cycle during the photon's progress through the polarizer*. That

will allow the *whole* photon energy to be maintained by giving enough time for the *full* \mathbf{E} to rotate until $\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c = m\pi$. Then, we suppose that when the photon reaches this point within the polarizer, its full energy can be absorbed by an atom in the polarizer, after which there is also a chance that the atom will emit a new photon of the same energy, but oscillating in the direction of the polarization slit, due to the direction of atomic lattice of the polarizer's inner slit edge. The details of whether this happens or not and our lack of knowledge of those details leads to the net effect of the *pass probability* being $|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}|^2$, while also allowing continuity of the total \mathbf{E} and its oscillation phase and accounting for its change in polarization.

Then, suppose that, given that the photon is not simply absorbed and that a transmission has happened, the probability that it is transmitted with no change in its phase is $p_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{c}, t) \equiv |c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}|$ (not squared), while the probability that it is transmitted with a random change in each photon's phase is $p_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{c}, t) \equiv 1 - |c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}|$.

Therefore, at all general values of $\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c$, the fact that passed photons must have the same electric field magnitude as input photons means that the right side of (50) gives the proper form of a passed photon but with \mathbf{c}' taking on its general definition from (49), as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}'_{\gamma, \tau_1} &\equiv |\mathbf{E}|\mathbf{c}' = |\mathbf{E}|\text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c})\mathbf{c}; & p_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{c}, t) \\ \mathbf{E}'_{\gamma, \tau_2} &\equiv |\mathbf{E}|\tilde{\mathbf{c}}' = |\mathbf{E}|\text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c + \tilde{\phi}})\mathbf{c}; & p_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{c}, t), \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

where $\tilde{\phi} \in [0, 2\pi)$ is a random phase angle that is generally different for each photon in that transmission case and $\tilde{\mathbf{c}}' \equiv \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c + \tilde{\phi}})\mathbf{c}$.

Thus, photons pass the polarizer with probability $|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}|^2$, and (51) gives their field, with *magnitude* $|\mathbf{E}|$ and *direction* of either $\mathbf{c}' \equiv \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c})\mathbf{c}$ or $\tilde{\mathbf{c}}' \equiv \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c + \tilde{\phi}})\mathbf{c}$ depending on transmission type.

Then, since the act of postselection for nonvacuum outcomes will effectively cause us to renormalize, we will lose the probability factor of $|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}|^2$. Since the time average of $|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}|^2$ is $\frac{1}{2}$, its net effect is to reduce the overall average intensity by $\frac{1}{2}$, reducing the electric field by $1/\sqrt{2}$, which can then either be treated by expressing things in units of $|\mathbf{E}|/\sqrt{2}$, or by normalizing the results by the peak average spin-component value over all the detector angles which is $|\mathbf{E}|/\sqrt{2}$. So, in units of $|\mathbf{E}|/\sqrt{2}$, the component of a passed photon's electric field is, for $k \in \{1, 2\}$,

$$\frac{\mathbf{c} \cdot \mathbf{E}'_{\gamma, \tau_k}}{|\mathbf{E}|/\sqrt{2}} = \begin{cases} \sqrt{2}\text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}); & p_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{c}, t) \\ \sqrt{2}\text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c + \tilde{\phi}}); & p_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{c}, t). \end{cases} \quad (52)$$

The probability of type-1 transmission times the electric field component of a passed photon in these units is

$$C_{C, \tau_1}(\mathbf{c}, t) \equiv p_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{c}, t) \frac{\mathbf{c} \cdot \mathbf{E}'_{\gamma, \tau_1}}{|\mathbf{E}|/\sqrt{2}} = \sqrt{2}c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c} \equiv C_C(\mathbf{c}, t), \quad (53)$$

which yields the *classical measurement functions* in (34) as $C_C(\mathbf{c}, t) = A_C(\mathbf{a}, t)$ when $\theta_c \rightarrow \theta_a$, and $C_C(\mathbf{c}, t) = B_C(\mathbf{b}, t)$ when $\theta_c \rightarrow \theta_b$ and $\phi_0 \rightarrow \phi_0 + \pi$.

The probability of type-2 transmission times the electric field component of a passed photon in these units is

$$\begin{aligned} C_{C, \tau_2}(\mathbf{c}, t) &\equiv p_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{c}, t) \frac{\mathbf{c} \cdot \mathbf{E}'_{\gamma, \tau_2}}{|\mathbf{E}|/\sqrt{2}} \\ &= \sqrt{2}(1 - |c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}|)\text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c + \tilde{\phi}}), \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

but averages to 0, so it does not affect the total mean.

We can then take the sign of (53) and (54) to get

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{c}, t) &\equiv \text{sgn}_2[C_{C, \tau_1}(\mathbf{c}, t)] = \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}) \equiv C(\mathbf{c}, t), \\ C_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{c}, t) &\equiv \text{sgn}_2[C_{C, \tau_2}(\mathbf{c}, t)] = \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c + \tilde{\phi}}), \end{aligned} \quad (55)$$

which gives the *quantum measurement functions* in (41) as $C(\mathbf{c}, t) = A(\mathbf{a}, t)$ when $\theta_c \rightarrow \theta_a$, and $C(\mathbf{c}, t) = B(\mathbf{b}, t)$ when $\theta_c \rightarrow \theta_b$ and $\phi_0 \rightarrow \phi_0 + \pi$. Thus, from (55) we get

$$\begin{aligned} A_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{a}, t) &\equiv \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a}); & p_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{a}, t) &\equiv |c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a}| \\ A_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{a}, t) &\equiv \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a + \tilde{\phi}_A}); & p_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{a}, t) &\equiv 1 - |c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a}| \\ B_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{b}, t) &\equiv \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b}); & p_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{b}, t) &\equiv |c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b}| \\ B_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{b}, t) &\equiv \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b + \tilde{\phi}_B}); & p_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{b}, t) &\equiv 1 - |c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b}|, \\ A_{\text{CPQ}}(\mathbf{a}, t) &\equiv p_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{a}, t)|\mathbf{A}|A_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{a}, t) + p_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{a}, t)|\mathbf{A}|A_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{a}, t) \\ B_{\text{CPQ}}(\mathbf{b}, t) &\equiv p_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{b}, t)|\mathbf{B}|B_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{b}, t) + p_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{b}, t)|\mathbf{B}|B_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{b}, t), \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

where $\tilde{\phi}_A$ is a different random phase shift for each photon at A , and similarly for $\tilde{\phi}_B$, where $|\mathbf{A}| = |\mathbf{B}| = \sqrt{2}$ here, so $A_{\text{CPQ}}(\mathbf{a}, t)$ and $B_{\text{CPQ}}(\mathbf{b}, t)$ are the *conditionally probabilistic quantum measurement functions* for the two-type transmission model (*and they are local*).

The fact that our model has two probabilistic transmission cases is to specifically motivate how loss of information can lead to the observed mean values in a locally real situation. In this case, *the probability p_{τ_1} of the phase-preserved transmission case will naturally ensure the proper spin-component magnitude despite our lack of information about that magnitude*.

Furthermore, in the product average, all terms involving a sign of a cosine of randomized phase will time average to 0, and we will be left with the proper product average at the end, despite our lack of knowledge about any of the spin-component magnitudes or which type of transmission is happening. Thus we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^T \frac{1}{T} dt &= 1 \\ \int_0^T \frac{1}{T} A_{\text{CPQ}}(\mathbf{a}, t) B_{\text{CPQ}}(\mathbf{b}, t) dt &= -c_{\theta_{a,b}}, \\ \int_0^T \frac{1}{T} A_{\text{CPQ}}(\mathbf{a}, t) dt &= 0, \\ \int_0^T \frac{1}{T} B_{\text{CPQ}}(\mathbf{b}, t) dt &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

which shows that entirely local functions can give rise to the physical averages we observe *and* accounts for the quantized measurement results, where here the factor of $\sqrt{2}$ can be viewed either as part of the units or as a scale factor of the measurement functions $A_{\tau_k}(\mathbf{b}, t)$ and $B_{\tau_k}(\mathbf{b}, t)$, or can simply be viewed as renormalization factors to the highest product average over all $\theta_{a,b}$.

Figure 3 shows a simulation of this specific model, where measured values are only ± 1 , and the two transmission types are implemented probabilistically with a

random variable. This test shows that there exists a classical explanation for how we can get quantized measurements and still achieve the observed mean values from properly local measurement functions and a local PDF.

FIG. 3: (color online) Simulation of time-based measurements to get the spin-component product average and lone component averages for our local HV model in the two-type transmission model of (56) using only *quantized measured values*. At each of 80 values of $\theta_{a,b}$, for each of 10^4 trials, a random value of t is produced between 0 and $T = 1$ to get ωt . Then a random number in $[0, 1]$ is used to get $p_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{a}, t)$ and $p_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{a}, t)$ for photon A and a different random number yields $p_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{b}, t)$ and $p_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{b}, t)$ for B . If a given random number is between 0 and $p_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{a}, t)$ the type-1 quantum measurement function $A_{\tau_1}(\mathbf{a}, t)$ is used, otherwise the type-2 function $A_{\tau_2}(\mathbf{a}, t)$ is used, which involves a random phase shift; similarly for B . Then the average values of all products over all trials for a particular $\theta_{a,b}$ were computed and plotted as experimental estimators for $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ and similarly for the lone-component averages.

Note that if these mechanisms are what actually happens, the classical and quantum measurement functions we have defined in (53) and line 1 in (55) are merely the type-1 parts, while (54) and line 2 in (55) are the type-2 parts. This means that a fully deterministic set of measurement functions would also require us to know exactly when which transmission type happened. In a truly classical case, this might be possible if we knew the phase of the photons upon creation and if we could measure the electric field accurately at the detector; we could simply postselect away any photons whose fields did not have a phase compatible with type-1 transmission, and then because we could measure the electric field, we would get the full spin component, which would make up for the loss of the probability factor in the postselection, and we would again arrive at the original classical measurement functions. (That would be effectively postselecting for only type-1 transmission coincidences.)

However, if this two-type transmission mechanism is present and the electric field cannot be measured directly, then the probabilistic nature of $A_{\text{CPQ}}(\mathbf{a}, t)$ and $B_{\text{CPQ}}(\mathbf{b}, t)$ from (56) may make tests of their validity generally impractical. But that is acceptable here be-

cause we are merely trying to show how loss of information can give rise to what we perceive, while still permitting a locally real system to exist.

Thus, we now have a consistent plausible explanation for how a locally real system can yield discrete results and still give rise to the proper spin statistics, despite our lack of knowledge of the specific real values of the quantities, and we have motivated both the classical and quantum measurement functions.

Now that we have a physical motivation for how the quantum measurement functions might arise and thus keep us from knowing the classical spin-component magnitudes even if they really do exist, we now look at what happens to the local HV model if we are not able to obtain this information.

C. Local HV Model + Ignorance of Spin Magnitude Yields an Effectively Nonlocal HV Model

In Sec. IV B, we saw a plausible explanation for how all-or-nothing absorption of particles can lead to effective loss of information about spin-component magnitudes and give rise to the quantum measurement functions we observe, *while still maintaining local realism*.

But suppose we did not have any idea about the two-type transmission model. What statistical framework would we obtain if the resulting quantum measurement functions from Sec. IV B were correct but we did not know anything else? Would our ignorance make this inherently local system seem nonlocal?

To account for this loss of information in our statistical description, first note that the four main physical facts still hold true, based on what we observe;

$$\begin{aligned} \langle I \rangle &= 1 \\ \langle \sigma_a \sigma_b \rangle &= -c_{\theta_{a,b}} \\ \langle \sigma_a \rangle &= 0 \\ \langle \sigma_b \rangle &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

Next, we want to rewrite (58) in terms of the quantum measurement functions, but we cannot simply borrow the spin-component magnitudes from the local HV model to make the PDF because they do not appear in all four of these relations, which would prevent us from getting a simple set of equations to solve for probabilities. However, their dependence on \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} does hint that we might need to consider an *effective* PDF that depends on those, so we can express these four physical facts as

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\phi_0}^{2\pi+\phi_0} \rho(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \lambda) d\lambda &= 1 \\ \int_{\phi_0}^{2\pi+\phi_0} \rho(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \lambda) A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) d\lambda &= -c_{\theta_{a,b}} \\ \int_{\phi_0}^{2\pi+\phi_0} \rho(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \lambda) A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) d\lambda &= 0 \\ \int_{\phi_0}^{2\pi+\phi_0} \rho(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \lambda) B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) d\lambda &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

where $\rho(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ is some new PDF that takes into account our ignorance of the spin-component magnitudes, and we have converted from time to the hidden variable $\lambda \equiv$

$\omega t + \phi_0$, so $d\lambda \equiv \omega dt$, $\lambda(T) \equiv \omega T + \phi_0 = 2\pi + \phi_0$, $\lambda(0) \equiv \phi_0$, and $t = \frac{1}{\omega}(\lambda - \phi_0)$, so the quantum measurement functions in terms of λ are

$$\begin{aligned} A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) &\equiv \text{sgn}_2(c_{\lambda - \theta_a}) \\ B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) &\equiv \text{sgn}_2(c_{\lambda + \pi - \theta_b}). \end{aligned} \quad (60)$$

Then, for consistency with Bell's derivations, we can use the fact from (60) that $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) = -A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ (although ironically this has no important effect on our results) to rewrite (59) as

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{\phi_0}^{2\pi + \phi_0} \rho(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \lambda) d\lambda = 1 \\ & - \int_{\phi_0}^{2\pi + \phi_0} \rho(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \lambda) A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) d\lambda = -c_{\theta_{a,b}} \\ & \int_{\phi_0}^{2\pi + \phi_0} \rho(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \lambda) A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) d\lambda = 0 \\ & \int_{\phi_0}^{2\pi + \phi_0} \rho(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \lambda) A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) d\lambda = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

Here, given (60), we can explicitly identify regions of λ in which $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ and $A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ have a fixed value combination. Thus, for a given pair of detector angles, the integrals in (61) break up into many regions of λ so we can *regroup them as sums of possibly noncontiguous piecewise integrations for which the values of $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ and $A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ are fixed and can come out of the integrals.*

The resulting quantities are four linear combinations of piecewise integrals, which lets us rewrite (61) as

$$\begin{aligned} p_{++} + p_{+-} + p_{-+} + p_{--} &= 1 \\ -p_{++} + p_{+-} + p_{-+} - p_{--} &= -c_{\theta_{a,b}} \\ p_{++} + p_{+-} - p_{-+} - p_{--} &= 0 \\ p_{++} - p_{+-} + p_{-+} - p_{--} &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (62)$$

where we have abbreviated the integral sums such as $p_{jk} \equiv \int_{jk} \rho(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \lambda) d\lambda$ for the sum of all regions where $\{j, k\} \equiv \{A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda), A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)\}$. But (62) is exactly the same as (24), so its solutions match (26) as

$$\begin{aligned} p_{++} &= \frac{1}{4}(1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ p_{+-} &= \frac{1}{4}(1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ p_{-+} &= \frac{1}{4}(1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ p_{--} &= \frac{1}{4}(1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}}), \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

which is a valid PDF and is *effectively nonlocal* due to its dependence on relative detector angle $\theta_{a,b}$.

The only difference from Sec. III B is that here we have *explicit quantum measurement functions* $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ and $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ in (60) arising from a fully *local* HV model, and it is only our lack of knowledge of the spin-component magnitudes (due to all-or-nothing absorption) that leads to the *appearance* of nonlocal behavior.

In this representation, the *values* of $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ and $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ are *fixed* for a given index pair, and since only their *values* remain in the discrete formulation (and as such, do not depend on any variables in these regions), it is more appropriate to define *measurement value* functions, given by

$$\xi_{q_1}^{(A)} \equiv \begin{cases} +1; & q_1 = 1 \\ -1; & q_1 = 2 \end{cases}; \quad \xi_{q_2}^{(B)} \equiv \begin{cases} +1; & q_2 = 1 \\ -1; & q_2 = 2 \end{cases}, \quad (64)$$

where we emphasize that $\xi_{q_1}^{(A)}$ and $\xi_{q_2}^{(B)}$ have no dependence on any variables because these are just possible *values*. Then, (59) takes the discrete statistical form

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{q_1, q_2=1,1}^{2,2} p_{q_1, q_2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = 1 \\ &\sum_{q_1, q_2=1,1}^{2,2} p_{q_1, q_2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \xi_{q_1}^{(A)} \xi_{q_2}^{(B)} = -c_{\theta_{a,b}} \\ &\sum_{q_1, q_2=1,1}^{2,2} p_{q_1, q_2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \xi_{q_1}^{(A)} = 0 \\ &\sum_{q_1, q_2=1,1}^{2,2} p_{q_1, q_2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \xi_{q_2}^{(B)} = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

where $\xi_{q_1}^{(A)}$ is the constant-value analogue to $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ and $\xi_{q_2}^{(B)}$ is the analogue to $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$, and where we have returned to using $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ instead of $-A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ because using $-A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ has no important effect on the results other than shuffling the probabilities, and this way is more consistent with our connections of HV theories to general quantum theory in Sec. VI. Thus the probabilities are

$$\begin{aligned} p_{1,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) &\equiv \frac{1}{4}(1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ p_{1,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) &\equiv \frac{1}{4}(1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ p_{2,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) &\equiv \frac{1}{4}(1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ p_{2,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) &\equiv \frac{1}{4}(1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}}), \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

and the sign flip in front of $c_{\theta_{a,b}}$ from what it was in (63) is due to the extra minus sign in line 2 of (61) that would cancel it in $-c_{\theta_{a,b}}$ on the right side, which was from using $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) = -A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ which is unnecessary here since our explicit measurement functions already satisfy that.

It is important to note here that since the *measurement values* $\xi_{q_1}^{(A)}$ and $\xi_{q_2}^{(B)}$ do not depend on anything, the discrete statistical formulation in (66) is a *histographic* representation of outcomes after many trials. In other words, since λ does not appear explicitly in (65), if we try to make a *new* hidden variable $\tilde{\lambda}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ out of these indices that proceeds in the order of (66) in time, it will be distinctly different from λ , related to it only in a non-local way, and likely causing λ to change discontinuously (which is due to the sum over possibly noncontiguous regions of λ that was used to get the discrete model), and will also implicitly define new quantum measurement functions to account for the artificial time-progression, again due to lumping all such regions together.

Therefore, there is not much advantage to converting the discrete model to a new continuous hidden variable. Rather, the important observation is that *this model agrees exactly with what Bell's model would have been if he had included the lone spin-component averages*, as seen by comparing it to the results of Sec. III B.

Thus, we have just shown that, starting from a locally real classical HV model, if we ignore (or do not have access to) the magnitude information about the spin components, the physical requirements of the system lead us to reorganize the model into a naturally *effectively non-local* discrete probability distribution. Put more simply,

local HV + some ignorance = effectively nonlocal HV

(67)

where an important point to acknowledge is that this ignorance is the classical kind, where the system really *does* have spin-component magnitudes, but we as humans for some reason just do not *know* them.

The *mechanism* for our lack of knowledge of the spin-component magnitudes might be simply the all-or-nothing absorption of photons that happens in the polarizer part of the detector as suggested in Sec. IV B, but this does not necessarily have to be quantum-mechanical in origin. For instance we could achieve the same thing with rotating wooden cylinders with a reference radius painted on them and a classically controlled mechanical arm that intercepts the cylinders probabilistically based on the square of the cosine of the angle that their reference radius makes with the direction angle of such a mechanical polarizer, and in the pass-case, passes them probabilistically based on type-1 or type-2 transmission with a random phase-shift in the type-2 case.

In other words, this missing information *does not have to be because of some fundamental intrinsic probability* of the special kind espoused by most interpretations of quantum mechanics, but rather it can arise from a regular classical system where we simply just do not know about some parts of it, which is what gives rise to *classical probability*, the regular nonquantum kind.

The key difference between this model and other non-local HV models is that this one arises from a *local* HV theory. And in particular, our model also predicts the exact values of the measurement results in time, as long as we know the initial conditions.

Perhaps the most interesting part of all of this is that it shows that *both QM and nonlocal HV theories are actually compatible with an underlying classically local reality* (whether or not such a local structure is true physically).

Next, in Sec. V, we revisit Bell’s inequality to show why his oversight of not including the lone spin-component averages and more importantly *not including the spin-component magnitudes* in his model led to the wrong inequality, and to see if we can derive an analogous inequality for the classical local model of Sec. IV A. After that, in Sec. VI we show how to convert any quantum system to an effectively nonlocal HV model, and then in Sec. VII, we show how to explicitly construct a *local* HV model for any multipartite discrete quantum system.

D. A Way to Use Quantized Measurement Results in a Local HV Model without Two-Type Transmission

So far, we have shown two examples of a local HV model that agrees with QM; one that uses classical measurement functions with full spin-component magnitudes in Sec. IV A, and another that utilizes conditionally probabilistic quantum measurement functions in the two-type transmission model of Sec. IV B.

However, if we simply use the quantum measurement functions of (41) without the two-type transmission model, they lack the proper weighting to agree with QM.

Here we show how to adapt our local HV theory so that the physical facts of quantized measurement results are still predicted by the quantum measurement functions of (41), while also producing mean values that agree with QM without resorting to the two-type transmission model of Sec. IV B.

The key idea here is that if the quantized measurement results really are predicted by the quantum measurement functions, then a particular result actually *implies* that the full classical measurement function’s value is what determines it in the case where we only have partial information but the actual value still exists.

Therefore, we can use the full classical measurement function value as a *representative value* of each actual measurement, so it acts as an “*effective eigenvalue*.” (As we mention several times, eigenvalues are not generally what are measured in QM – we measure *events*, and then we *represent* them as eigenvalues in our theoretical models, so this concept is compatible with that paradigm.)

Furthermore, if the classical measurement function’s value is really what happens, then there’s no need for us to jump to assigning $+1$ or -1 to each measurement. We can simply use the recorded time t and then the *classical measurement function itself determines both the quantized eigenvalue ± 1 and the continuous effective eigenvalue to use to represent each measurement*.

This procedure is valid if the quantized measurement values we perceive arise from some loss of information that is actually there. In that case, the proper measured value would be the actual value of the classical variable, and only those values would lead to the proper mean value. So our motivation here is that if our local HV model correctly describes the system, it is valid to use the model itself to *calculate an indirectly measured value* from more fundamental measured values such as ϕ_0 , t , and detector angles θ_a , θ_b . The indirectly measured value can then function as an effective eigenvalue for each measurement. (This is actually a standard procedure. For instance, reactance is indirectly measured using its theoretical definition, even though it is the imaginary part of impedance and “cannot be measured directly.”)

To get an idea of how to implement this, suppose that in an ideal case, ϕ_0 from Sec. IV A is known for each prepared particle pair and that time-of-measurement t after preparation is recorded with the spin-component measurements $A_M \in \pm 1$ and $B_M \in \pm 1$.

Then a typical list of measurements might look like

$$\begin{array}{cccccc} t & \phi_0 & \theta_a & \theta_b & A_M & B_M \\ \hline t_1 & \phi_{0,1} & \theta_{a,1} & \theta_{b,1} & +1 & -1 \\ t_2 & \phi_{0,2} & \theta_{a,2} & \theta_{b,2} & -1 & -1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \end{array}, \quad (68)$$

where θ_a and θ_b are typically constant as a number of identically-prepared trials are done for that angle combination, and ω is the photons’ angular frequency.

If our local HV model is valid for the system, then there was actually no need to record A_M and B_M , because they are merely functions of the other measured data.

Therefore, for each trial, we can simply calculate *indirectly measured values* A_{C_M} and B_{C_M} for each trial as

$$\begin{array}{cccccc} t & \phi_0 & \theta_a & \theta_b & A_{C_M} & B_{C_M} \\ t_1 & \phi_{0,1} & \theta_{a,1} & \theta_{b,1} & \sqrt{2}c_{\omega t_1 + \phi_{0,1} - \theta_{a,1}} & \sqrt{2}c_{\omega t_1 + \phi_{0,1} + \pi - \theta_{b,1}} \\ t_2 & \phi_{0,2} & \theta_{a,2} & \theta_{b,2} & \sqrt{2}c_{\omega t_2 + \phi_{0,2} - \theta_{a,2}} & \sqrt{2}c_{\omega t_2 + \phi_{0,2} + \pi - \theta_{b,2}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \end{array} \quad (69)$$

If the local HV model is physically valid, then

$$\begin{aligned} A_M &= \text{sgn}_2(A_{C_M}) = \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a}) \\ B_M &= \text{sgn}_2(B_{C_M}) = \text{sgn}_2(c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b}), \end{aligned} \quad (70)$$

for all trials, so our quantized results of ± 1 would match up with the sign of full values A_{C_M} and B_{C_M} that we cannot directly measure (for whatever reason).

Thus, if we compute $A_{C_M} B_{C_M}$ for each k th trial of ν total trials of a given value of $\theta_{a,b} \equiv \theta_a - \theta_b$, then an estimator for the spin-component product is

$$\frac{1}{\nu} \sum_{k=1}^{\nu} A_{C_M,k} B_{C_M,k} \approx -c_{\theta_{a,b}} = \langle \sigma_a \sigma_b \rangle, \quad (71)$$

where the approximation is a perfect equality in the limit of infinite trials $\nu \rightarrow \infty$ (and similarly for the lone spin-component averages which are 0 in the ideal limit.)

Note that we are *not* claiming that the specific measurement functions from Sec. IV A are what actually determines all results for two spin 1/2 particles in the singlet state; merely that it is one possible solution for a local HV model that agrees with QM, and here we are simply showing how to adapt that model to handle quantization without the need for two-type transmission.

Since experimental data using ± 1 already naturally yields $\langle \sigma_a \sigma_b \rangle$ without the need for effective eigenvalues, it seems clear that this particular interpretation of our local HV model is *not* the true description of reality since its predictions for A_M and B_M need to be converted to A_{C_M} and B_{C_M} . However, the two-type transmission model of Sec. IV B *could* still be a valid local HV model that agrees with both QM and experiment. Nevertheless, the effective eigenvalue method is still a valid local HV model that agrees with QM without two-type transmission.

We now take a deeper look at how to derive correct Bell inequalities and consider what this means for all previous claims about the meanings of Bell-inequality violations.

V. CORRECTED DERIVATION OF BELL'S INEQUALITY

In Sec. IV, we found that if we let the model be fully classical, that is, let the spin components have continuous magnitudes, we get the correct statistics *and* still get quantized spin functions by taking the sign of the classical measurement functions.

We then found that if we accept our ignorance of the spin-component magnitudes in this classical local HV model, we can still use the physical facts of the system

(such as the lone spin-component averages, which Bell ignored) to deduce a discrete, effectively nonlocal HV model with a nonlocal PDF (but in which we still get deterministic quantum measurement functions through its underlying local HV model).

However, this effectively nonlocal HV model uses *measurement value* variables $\xi_{q_1}^{(A)}$ and $\xi_{q_2}^{(B)}$ which are different from measurement *functions* $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ and $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ because $\xi_{q_1}^{(A)}$ and $\xi_{q_2}^{(B)}$ do not depend on either the detector angles or the hidden variable; they are merely the possible *values* of the measurement functions, to be grouped with the appropriate categorical probabilities in the discrete distribution.

As we will see in Sec. VI, the appearance of $\xi_{q_1}^{(A)}$ and $\xi_{q_2}^{(B)}$ as value functions independent of other variables is a common occurrence when constructing HV theories of general quantum systems, and they have a very simple “physical” interpretation as *eigenvalues*.

For now, we want to see how to construct a “corrected Bell inequality” based off of the new results from Sec. IV. In other words, since Bell did not construct a proper local HV system (since he omitted the lone-spin component averages and presumed quantization at a fundamental level), his inequality does not reflect an accurate constraint on local HV theories.

Therefore, here, we will check three *corrected* Bell inequalities; (i) that of the fully classical local HV model of Sec. IV A, (ii) that of the discrete-distribution effectively nonlocal HV model of Sec. IV C we got by ignoring the spin magnitudes in the local HV model, and (iii) the CHSH inequality, to show that this result is more far-reaching than Bell’s original inequality.

A. Valid Bell-Type Inequality for the Local HV Model

Recall from (36) that we found

$$\int_0^T \rho_C(t) A_C(\mathbf{a}, t) B_C(\mathbf{b}, t) dt = -c_{\theta_{a,b}}, \quad (72)$$

with classical PDF and classical measurement functions

$$\rho_C(t) \equiv \frac{1}{T}, \quad \begin{aligned} A_C(\mathbf{a}, t) &\equiv \sqrt{2}c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a}, \\ B_C(\mathbf{b}, t) &\equiv \sqrt{2}c_{\omega t + \phi_0 + \pi - \theta_b} = -\sqrt{2}c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_b}, \end{aligned} \quad (73)$$

where t acts as the hidden variable, and from (73),

$$B_C(\mathbf{b}, t) = -A_C(\mathbf{b}, t). \quad (74)$$

So, following Bell, put (74) into (72) and define it as

$$P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \equiv - \int_0^T \rho_C(t) A_C(\mathbf{a}, t) A_C(\mathbf{b}, t) dt, \quad (75)$$

which, by (72), *is already different than Bell’s derivation because we know that $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ of the local HV model yields the correct physical value*, however we will ignore this and proceed as closely to Bell’s derivation as possible.

Now plug (40) into (75) to get it in terms of the quantum measurement functions as

$$P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = -\int_0^T 2|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a}| |c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_b}| \rho_C(t) A(\mathbf{a}, t) A(\mathbf{b}, t) dt, \quad (76)$$

where here we note that the extra magnitude factors cannot be lumped with the PDF for a new PDF, and their dependence on detector angles will affect the rest of the derivation in a nontrivial way by making it harder to get a third average involved. But continuing, we then have

$$P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) = -\int_0^T 2|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a}| |c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}| \rho_C(t) A(\mathbf{a}, t) A(\mathbf{c}, t) dt, \quad (77)$$

so their difference is

$$P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) = -\int_0^T 2|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a}| \rho_C(t) \times \left[|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_b}| A(\mathbf{a}, t) A(\mathbf{b}, t) - |c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}| A(\mathbf{a}, t) A(\mathbf{c}, t) \right] dt, \quad (78)$$

which already shows that the extra magnitude factors will cause some issues, but again, proceeding as close to Bell as possible, we insert $1 = A(\mathbf{b}, t)A(\mathbf{b}, t)$ into the second term and factor out $A(\mathbf{a}, t)A(\mathbf{b}, t)$ as

$$P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) = -\int_0^T 2|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a}| \rho_C(t) A(\mathbf{a}, t) A(\mathbf{b}, t) \times \left[|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_b}| - |c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}| A(\mathbf{b}, t) A(\mathbf{c}, t) \right] dt. \quad (79)$$

Here, we know that we want to end up with a term that simplifies to $P(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})$ after using the triangle inequality, and an important part of that in Bell's derivation is that we obtained the factor $[1 - A(\mathbf{b}, t)A(\mathbf{c}, t)]$, which is always nonnegative, and therefore came out of the absolute value and let us achieve $P(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})$.

However, we cannot factor out the remaining magnitudes in the last big factor in (79), and they prevent it from being always nonnegative. Therefore, taking absolute values and applying the triangle inequality gives

$$|P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| \leq M(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, T, \phi_0), \quad (80)$$

where its maximum-value function is

$$M(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, T, \phi_0) \equiv \int_0^T 2|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a}| \frac{1}{T} \left[|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_b}| + |c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}| A(\mathbf{b}, t) A(\mathbf{c}, t) \right] dt, \quad (81)$$

which shows that we do not get an actual appearance of $P(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})$, and we cannot easily simplify this further due to the absolute value of the last big factor.

However, this result does not invalidate anything – it just means the inequality is not so tidy. The left side of (80) allows us to use the values from QM (or from experiment), while the right side of (80) contains elements specifically derived from this local HV model (similar to

the way the right side of Bell's inequality was derived from his alleged local HV model).

Therefore (80) is the Bell-type inequality for our local HV model, where we used (73) to get $\rho_C(t)$ and (41) for $A(\mathbf{b}, t)$ and $A(\mathbf{c}, t)$ to compute the integral in (81).

As Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 show, (80) *is always true for every combination of angles we try* (guaranteed by the fact that $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ already agrees with QM). Thus, when a *proper* local HV model is constructed, *it leads to a Bell-type inequality that is never violable by the results of QM (and also experiment)*, meaning that all experimental data will satisfy (80), within the margins of experimental error.

FIG. 4: (color online) Top surface in warm hues is $M \equiv M(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, T, \phi_0)$ on the right in (80) given in (81), and the lower surface (in cool hues from cyan to magenta) is the left side of (80), with the quantum-mechanical results plugged in as $|P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| = |-c_{\theta_{a,b}} + c_{\theta_{a,c}}|$ which is seen to be always less than or equal to M (with slivers of those cooler colors showing at points where the two are equal), all with $\theta_a = 2\pi$. Fig. 5 shows the same test for a few values of θ_c .

FIG. 5: (color online) Alternative perspective showing that upper limit $M \equiv M(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, T, \phi_0)$ from (80) and (81) is not exceeded by $|P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| = |-c_{\theta_{a,b}} + c_{\theta_{a,c}}|$ from (80). Both this figure and Fig. 4 support the proof that M of (81) is a valid upper limit that cannot be violated by quantum-mechanical (or experimental) results. Thus when Bell inequalities are properly derived, there can be no violations.

For a particular example, using the situation of (13), where $\theta_a = 0$, $\theta_b = \frac{\pi}{2}$, $\theta_c = \frac{\pi}{4}$, and taking $\phi_0 = 0$ and $T = 1$ [s], (80) yields

$$0.707 \leq 0.717 \quad (\text{true!}), \quad (82)$$

which shows that there is actually no Bell violation predicted here, whereas Bell's flawed model did predict a violation in (13).

At this point, it may seem as if we are somehow "reverse-sabotaging" the situation to work by allowing the continuous spin-component magnitudes, even though our premise for doing so (which was to model the suppositional local HV system as a truly classical system) was appropriate. But remember that this still allowed us to obtain *quantized* measurement functions when we upgraded to the two-type transmission model, so it is still actually compatible with the quantization requirement.

Note also that although the derivation of (80) did not take the lone spin-component averages into account explicitly, they are present *implicitly* since the classical measurement functions *obey them already*.

Most importantly, note that since the classical measurement functions of the local HV model already yield the same function for $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ as QM, we can actually tighten (80) to an exact equality as

$$|P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| = |-c_{\theta_{a,b}} + c_{\theta_{a,c}}| = |\mathbf{a} \cdot (\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{c})|, \quad (83)$$

which always agrees with QM. However, we derived (80) using a method as close to Bell's as possible to illustrate that doing so still does not yield a violable inequality.

But just to be thorough, let us now look at the Bell-type inequality for the effectively *nonlocal* HV model we obtained in Sec. V C.

B. Valid Bell-Type Inequality for the Discrete Effectively Nonlocal HV Model

In the effectively nonlocal HV model of Sec. IV C (that arose from the *local* HV model with loss of information of the spin-component magnitudes), the spin-component product average is, adapting (61) to the form of (65),

$$P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = - \sum_{q_1, q_2=1,2}^{2,2} p'_{q_1, q_2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \xi_{q_1}^{(A)} \xi_{q_2}^{(A)} = -c_{\theta_{a,b}}, \quad (84)$$

where, since $\xi_{q_1}^{(A)}$ is just the *value* variable from (64) for each measurement outcome, it does not depend on detector angle at all; it merely represents possible *values* in this reorganization of the problem. Note that we discretized (61) instead of using (65) because (61) already incorporates Bell's application of $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) = -A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$. Meanwhile, the probabilities are, from (63),

$$\begin{aligned} p'_{1,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) &\equiv p_{++} = \frac{1}{4}(1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ p'_{1,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) &\equiv p_{+-} = \frac{1}{4}(1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ p'_{2,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) &\equiv p_{-+} = \frac{1}{4}(1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ p'_{2,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) &\equiv p_{--} = \frac{1}{4}(1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}}). \end{aligned} \quad (85)$$

To keep everything as transparent as possible, we write out each term in (84) as

$$\begin{aligned} P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = -[&p'_{1,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \xi_1^{(A)} \xi_1^{(A)} + p'_{1,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \xi_1^{(A)} \xi_2^{(A)} \\ &+ p'_{2,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \xi_2^{(A)} \xi_1^{(A)} + p'_{2,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \xi_2^{(A)} \xi_2^{(A)}], \end{aligned} \quad (86)$$

and for the moment, we ignore the fact that the squares of $\xi_{q_1}^{(A)}$ in first and last terms are 1 and that plugging in the probabilities will just give the correct physical answer.

Then, following Bell, replacing \mathbf{b} with \mathbf{c} in (86) gives

$$\begin{aligned} P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) = -[&p'_{1,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) \xi_1^{(A)} \xi_1^{(A)} + p'_{1,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) \xi_1^{(A)} \xi_2^{(A)} \\ &+ p'_{2,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) \xi_2^{(A)} \xi_1^{(A)} + p'_{2,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) \xi_2^{(A)} \xi_2^{(A)}], \end{aligned} \quad (87)$$

and subtracting (87) from (86) gives

$$\begin{aligned} P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) = -[&p'_{1,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - p'_{1,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})] \xi_1^{(A)} \xi_1^{(A)} \\ &- [p'_{1,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - p'_{1,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})] \xi_1^{(A)} \xi_2^{(A)} \\ &- [p'_{2,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - p'_{2,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})] \xi_2^{(A)} \xi_1^{(A)} \\ &- [p'_{2,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - p'_{2,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})] \xi_2^{(A)} \xi_2^{(A)}. \end{aligned} \quad (88)$$

At this point, Bell inserted $1 = A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$, to pull some factors out of the main sum, but here, the closest we can come to that is to insert a square of the value variables. The most general way we could do this is

$$\begin{aligned} P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) = -[&p'_{1,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - p'_{1,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})] \xi_1^{(A)} [\xi_a^{(A)} \xi_a^{(A)}] \xi_1^{(A)} \\ &- [p'_{1,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - p'_{1,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})] \xi_1^{(A)} [\xi_b^{(A)} \xi_b^{(A)}] \xi_2^{(A)} \\ &- [p'_{2,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - p'_{2,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})] \xi_2^{(A)} [\xi_c^{(A)} \xi_c^{(A)}] \xi_1^{(A)} \\ &- [p'_{2,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - p'_{2,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})] \xi_2^{(A)} [\xi_d^{(A)} \xi_d^{(A)}] \xi_2^{(A)}, \end{aligned} \quad (89)$$

where $a, b, c, d \in \{1, 2\}$, but regardless of what choices we make for a, b, c, d , the newly inserted factors cannot change the sign of each term, nor will any of the measurement values survive the triangle inequality or allow us to get something analogous to (10).

Here, before taking the absolute value and applying the triangle inequality, note that plugging in the probabilities from (85) for both sets of arguments merely leads to the right side being identical to the left. That is, this is *already* the answer, so it is already the tightest relation we could find. But, we could continue doggedly on by taking the absolute value and applying the triangle inequality, which gives

$$\begin{aligned} |P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| \leq &|p'_{1,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - p'_{1,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| \\ &+ |p'_{1,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - p'_{1,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| \\ &+ |p'_{2,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - p'_{2,1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| \\ &+ |p'_{2,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - p'_{2,2}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})|, \end{aligned} \quad (90)$$

and then plugging in from (85) gives

$$\begin{aligned} |P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| \leq &\left| \frac{1}{4} c_{\theta_{a,b}} - \frac{1}{4} c_{\theta_{a,c}} \right| \\ &+ \left| \frac{1}{4} - c_{\theta_{a,b}} + \frac{1}{4} c_{\theta_{a,c}} \right| \\ &+ \left| \frac{1}{4} - c_{\theta_{a,b}} + \frac{1}{4} c_{\theta_{a,c}} \right| \\ &+ \left| \frac{1}{4} c_{\theta_{a,b}} - \frac{1}{4} c_{\theta_{a,c}} \right| \\ |P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| \leq &| -c_{\theta_{a,b}} + c_{\theta_{a,c}} |, \end{aligned} \quad (91)$$

where we note that this could be further loosened to

$$|P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| \leq |c_{\theta_{a,b}}| + |c_{\theta_{a,c}}| \leq 2, \quad (92)$$

and thus (91) and (92) are the most faithful Bell-type inequality for the effectively nonlocal HV model because we followed all of Bell's steps as closely as possible.

However, noting that (92) unnecessarily *loosened* the relationship of (91), and that neither of them presents a natural way to involve $P(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})$, then we can really just rewrite (91) as

$$|P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| = |-c_{\theta_{a,b}} + c_{\theta_{a,c}}| = |\mathbf{a} \cdot (\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{c})|, \quad (93)$$

which again is the tightest kind of inequality; an *equality*, meaning that the effectively nonlocal HV model will satisfy this relation for all possible valid data within experimental error.

If we really wanted to involve $P(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})$, we could use the dot product on the right of (93) to rewrite it as

$$\begin{aligned} |P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| &= |\mathbf{a}| |\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{c}| |c_{\theta_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}-\mathbf{c}}}| \\ &= |\mathbf{a}| \sqrt{(\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{c}) \cdot (\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{c})} |c_{\theta_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}-\mathbf{c}}}| \\ &= |\mathbf{a}| \sqrt{|\mathbf{b}|^2 - 2\mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{c} + |\mathbf{c}|^2} |c_{\theta_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}-\mathbf{c}}}| \\ &= |c_{\theta_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}-\mathbf{c}}}| \sqrt{2[1 + P(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})]}, \end{aligned} \quad (94)$$

where $\theta_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}-\mathbf{c}}$ is the angle between \mathbf{a} and $\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{c}$, and we used the fact that all of these are unit vectors. But this is still just an equality. We could make it an inequality by using the fact that $|c_{\theta_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}-\mathbf{c}}}| \leq 1$ to get

$$|P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| \leq \sqrt{2[1 + P(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})]}, \quad (95)$$

but since (94) was already exact, all we did was *loosen* the relationship, so (95) works trivially for all detector angles, and again there will be no violations from any valid experimental data, even with this inclusion of $P(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})$.

So to summarize, using the effectively nonlocal HV model induced from the *local* HV model, we get three different Bell-type inequalities;

$$\begin{aligned} |P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| &= |\mathbf{a} \cdot (\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{c})| = |-c_{\theta_{a,b}} + c_{\theta_{a,c}}| \\ &= |c_{\theta_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}-\mathbf{c}}}| \sqrt{2[1 + P(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})]} \\ |P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| &\leq \sqrt{2[1 + P(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})]} \\ |P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| &\leq 2 \end{aligned}$$

(96)

and all of them are satisfied by *all* experimental data up to typical errors, with the top relation being the tightest one, achieving exact agreement, the second relation (the first inequality) being a bit looser, and the bottom relation being the loosest.

Therefore, here there is no need to check anything numerically, the first line in (96) shows that it will always work. Note also that the first result in (96), although derived from the effectively nonlocal HV model which came from our local HV model with some information removed, is exactly the same result we got in (28) when

we fixed Bell's original model by including the physical facts of lone spin-component averages.

Furthermore, these results extend beyond Bell's original inequality, as we show next.

C. Valid CHSH Inequality for Both the Effectively Nonlocal HV and Local HV Models

The CHSH inequality [8–10] is based on Bell's original arguments and therefore directly inherits his errors.

As presented by modern authors [11, 12], suppose four combinations of detector angles are used, two settings on each side, with vectors \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}' at A and \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}' at B .

Then defining a *compound observable* of Bell's measurement functions as

$$\begin{aligned} C(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}', \lambda) &\equiv A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) + A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)B(\mathbf{b}', \lambda) \\ &\quad + A(\mathbf{a}', \lambda)B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) - A(\mathbf{a}', \lambda)B(\mathbf{b}', \lambda), \end{aligned} \quad (97)$$

with the property that $C(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}', \lambda) \in \pm 2$, its mean can be written in terms of Bell's mean-value function as

$$\begin{aligned} Q(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}') &\equiv \int \rho(\lambda) C(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}', \lambda) d\lambda \\ &= P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) + P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}') + P(\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}'). \end{aligned} \quad (98)$$

Then, from Bell's inequality in (12) we know $|P(\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}')| \leq 1 + P(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}')$, and a similar derivation shows $|P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) + P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}')| \leq 1 - P(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}')$, so then

$$\begin{aligned} |Q(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}')| &= |P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) + P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}') + P(\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}')| \\ &\leq |P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) + P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}')| + |P(\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}')| \\ &\leq 1 - P(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}') + 1 + P(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}') = 2 \\ |Q(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}')| &\leq 2, \end{aligned} \quad (99)$$

which is a common form of the *CHSH inequality*. Then, since QM (and experiment) requires $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = -c_{\theta_{a,b}}$, if we choose a setting combination such as $\theta_a = \frac{\pi}{2}$, $\theta_b = \frac{3\pi}{4}$, $\theta_{a'} = \pi$, $\theta_{b'} = \frac{\pi}{4}$, putting it into (99) yields

$$2\sqrt{2} \leq 2 \quad (\text{false!}), \quad (100)$$

and that false statement is claimed to be further proof that local HV theories are incompatible with QM, and thus also with our experimental perception of reality.

However, as we showed in Sec. III, Bell's model did not take the lone-spin averages into account, and if he *had* included them, his HV model would have produced $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = -c_{\theta_{a,b}}$, meaning that the quantity $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = -\int \rho(\lambda) A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) d\lambda$ itself *is already equal to* $-c_{\theta_{a,b}}$ when those physical facts are taken into account.

Thus, Bell's corrected model would yield a corrected Bell's "inequality" of $|P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| = |\mathbf{a} \cdot (\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{c})| = |-c_{\theta_{a,b}} + c_{\theta_{a,c}}|$, and in that case, the corrected CHSH "inequality" should be

$$\begin{aligned} |Q(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}')| &= |\mathbf{a} \cdot (\mathbf{b} + \mathbf{b}') + \mathbf{a}' \cdot (\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{b}')| \\ &= |-c_{\theta_{a,b}} - c_{\theta_{a,b'}} - c_{\theta_{a',b}} + c_{\theta_{a',b'}}|, \end{aligned} \quad (101)$$

which is always satisfied since it is in exact agreement with QM, as seen by plugging in the same setting combination as in (100) which gives

$$2\sqrt{2} = 2\sqrt{2} \quad (\text{true!}). \quad (102)$$

As we discussed in Sec. III, the discrete probabilities that emerge in the corrected Bell's model make it *appear* to be *nonlocal* because they depend on $c_{\theta_{a,b}}$.

However, as shown in Sec. IV, this is merely an *effectively nonlocal* HV model because the exact same discrete probabilities emerge when we start from a truly *local* HV model and then omit our knowledge of the spin-component magnitudes, as seen in Sec. IV C by comparing (63) to (26).

But since the corrected Bell's model is equivalent to our *local* HV model with missing information, then to *get a proper assessment of the possible limitations of a truly local HV theory, we can use our local HV inequality* from (80), which was

$$|P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| \leq M(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, T, \phi_0), \quad (103)$$

where $M(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, T, \phi_0)$ is given in (81). (We could actually use (83) instead, which would yield the same result as (102), but we use (80) here since it was obtained by following Bell's steps as closely as possible, despite being a looser inequality.) Then, defining two versions of (103) based on whether the two mean values that lead to it are added or subtracted as

$$M_{\pm}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, T, \phi_0) \equiv \int_0^T 2|c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_a}| \frac{1}{T} \left| c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_b} \right. \\ \left. \pm |c_{\omega t + \phi_0 - \theta_c}| A(\mathbf{b}, t) A(\mathbf{c}, t) \right| dt, \quad (104)$$

so $M(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, T, \phi_0) = M_-(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, T, \phi_0)$ in (81), then *the correct CHSH inequality for a truly local HV model is*

$$|Q(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}')| = |P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) + P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}') + P(\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}')| \\ \leq |P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) + P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}')| + |P(\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}) - P(\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}')| \\ |Q(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}')| \leq M_+(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}', T, \phi_0) + M_-(\mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}', T, \phi_0) \quad (105)$$

[and really, (101) would be the tightest form of the correct CHSH inequality, since the local HV model yields that.]

As shown in Sec. V A, (103) is *always satisfied* by the results of QM, so (105) is *always satisfied* as well, which we can see by putting the same setting combination used in (100) into (105) to get

$$2\sqrt{2} \leq 2\sqrt{2} \quad (\text{true!}). \quad (106)$$

Therefore, any Bell-type inequalities, such as the CHSH inequality, that depend on Bell's inequality or similar assumptions are all invalid since we have shown that Bell's model and therefore his inequality are wrong.

Thus, *what prevents us from recreating Bell's original inequality is one of two things; in the local HV models, it is the involvement of the spin-component magnitudes, either as classically real parts of the spin, or as probabilities in a two-type transmission model; in the effectively*

nonlocal HV model, it is the probabilities' dependence on relative angle. Bell's omission of the lone spin averages and spin-component magnitudes is why his inequality is too tight to properly describe a local HV model.

Although we have only actually shown this for a two-qubit system in the Bohm-Aharonov-Bell example, we will now show how all of QM can be recast into the same form as the effectively nonlocal HV model we got by omitting information from our truly local HV model. Then in Sec. VII, we will show how a truly local HV model can be constructed for all multipartite discrete systems.

VI. EFFECTIVELY NONLOCAL HV MODELS FOR ALL DISCRETE QUANTUM SYSTEMS

Here we show how to properly generalize Bell's classical spin-component product average $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ to the case of any observable in N -partite quantum systems, achieving a general method for producing effectively nonlocal HV models that agree with QM, but that can also be shown to arise from truly *local* HV models in which some information about them is ignored.

In particular, in Sec. VI we show that it is always possible to find a strictly classical yet effectively nonlocal probability distribution that causes the measurement functions to always break up into a number of regions that guarantees any Bell inequalities derived will never be violated by QM (and therefore not by experiment either).

In Sec. VII, we will show how to construct a truly *local* HV model for any state of any multipartite quantum system, with a complete set of measurement functions that are truly local in the sense of only depending on their local detector vectors and whatever initial synchronization conditions were part of the multi-particle system's creation in some initially local region. (We will also show how such local HV models relate to nonlocal operators and time-evolution operations in QM.)

A. Eigenvalue Hypothesis for $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ and $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$

This investigation began with a hypothesis (which we will prove in the next few subsections of this paper) called the *eigenvalue hypothesis* (which we present here in the context of Bell's example):

In the mean-value formula (in Bell's notation),

$$P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \int \rho(\lambda) A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) d\lambda, \quad (107)$$

the measurement functions could be explained by the

Eigenvalue Hypothesis: The values ± 1 of the measurement functions $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ and $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ are *eigenvalues* of observables $\sigma_a^{(A)} \equiv \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(A)} \cdot \mathbf{a}$ and $\sigma_b^{(B)} \equiv \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(B)} \cdot \mathbf{b}$ in an effectively nonlocal HV model.

(108)

Next, we review a familiar concept that we call "rotational quantum-state tomography" which will give us the tools we need to support the eigenvalue hypothesis.

B. Rotational Quantum State Tomography Generates Effectively Nonlocal HV Models

Quantum state tomography is the method of using mean values of some tomographically complete set of observables to parameterize a quantum state [13, 14]. The term *tomography* is usually used to describe a *measurement* process, but here we use it to *also* describe the mathematical expansion of ρ that defines it.

In general, we need $n^2 - 1$ nonidentity observables to form a tomographically complete set, and they can all always be chosen to have Kronecker-product form in an N -mode system (such as $\Omega_{\mathbf{k}} \equiv \Omega_{k_1}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes \Omega_{k_N}^{(N)}$). In this section, for simplicity, we focus only on *one* product-form observable (letting us drop the indices), as

$$\Omega \equiv \Omega^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes \Omega^{(N)}, \quad (109)$$

and the mean value of Ω for a system in state ρ is

$$\Gamma_\Omega \equiv \text{tr}(\rho\Omega). \quad (110)$$

(A tomographically complete set $\{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}\}$ would be a *set* of mean values $\Gamma_{\mathbf{k} \neq \mathbf{0}} \equiv \Gamma_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k} \neq \mathbf{0}}} \equiv \text{tr}(\rho\Omega_{\mathbf{k}})$ which are the components of a Bloch-vector description of ρ [15–19].)

Now, since Ω is Hermitian, it has spectral decomposition $\Omega = \epsilon_\Omega \Lambda_\Omega \epsilon_\Omega^\dagger$, where ϵ_Ω is the unitary eigenvector matrix of Ω , and Λ_Ω is the diagonal matrix of real eigenvalues of Ω , and using this fact in (110) yields

$$\Gamma_\Omega = \text{tr}(\rho \epsilon_\Omega \Lambda_\Omega \epsilon_\Omega^\dagger) = \text{tr}(\epsilon_\Omega^\dagger \rho \epsilon_\Omega \Lambda_\Omega) \equiv \text{tr}(\rho_\Omega \Lambda_\Omega), \quad (111)$$

where the *rotated state* is

$$\rho_\Omega \equiv \epsilon_\Omega^\dagger \rho \epsilon_\Omega, \quad (112)$$

which we can think of as ρ unitarily “rotated” by ϵ_Ω^\dagger , the adjoint of the eigenvector matrix of observable Ω . Thus, (111) re-expresses the mean value Γ_Ω of observable Ω for the system in state ρ as a mean value of *diagonal observable* Λ_Ω for the system in *rotated state* ρ_Ω .

All of this is just “measurement in the basis of Ω ,” which is a standard procedure, but the formalism here is essential to our task. We call this method *rotational tomography* to distinguish it from projective-filtration tomography, for instance using unitary waveplates instead of specialized absorptive polarizing filters, but both methods are *mathematically* equivalent in their results.

It is most useful to write this diagonal observable as

$$\Lambda_\Omega = \bigotimes_{m=1}^N \Lambda_{\Omega^{(m)}}^{(m)} = \Lambda_{\Omega^{(1)}}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes \Lambda_{\Omega^{(N)}}^{(N)}, \quad (113)$$

where the mode- m eigenvalue matrix is

$$\Lambda_{\Omega^{(m)}}^{(m)} = \sum_{q_m=1}^{n_m} (\xi_{\Omega^{(m)}}^{(m)})_{q_m} |q_m^{(m)}\rangle \langle q_m^{(m)}| \equiv \sum_{q_m=1}^{n_m} \xi_{q_m}^{(m)} P_{q_m}^{(m)}, \quad (114)$$

where $\xi_{q_m}^{(m)} \equiv (\xi_{\Omega^{(m)}}^{(m)})_{q_m}$ is the q_m th eigenvalue of $\Omega^{(m)}$, $\xi_1^{(m)} \geq \cdots \geq \xi_{n_m}^{(m)}$, and

$$P_{q_m}^{(m)} \equiv |q_m^{(m)}\rangle \langle q_m^{(m)}| \quad (115)$$

are rank-1 projectors of the mode- m computational basis states. Note that the more explicit eigenvalue notation is to let us specify to *which observable in which mode* an eigenvalue belongs. Also, (113) and (114) are specifically for *product-form* observables, and do not hold in general for nonlocal observables, which we treat in Sec. VID.

The full form of (113) is then

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_\Omega &= \Lambda_{\Omega^{(1)}}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes \Lambda_{\Omega^{(N)}}^{(N)} \\ &= \left(\sum_{q_1=1}^{n_1} \xi_{q_1}^{(1)} P_{q_1}^{(1)} \right) \otimes \cdots \otimes \left(\sum_{q_N=1}^{n_N} \xi_{q_N}^{(N)} P_{q_N}^{(N)} \right) \\ &= \sum_{q_1, \dots, q_N=1, \dots, 1}^{n_1, \dots, n_N} (\xi_{q_1}^{(1)} \cdots \xi_{q_N}^{(N)}) P_{q_1}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes P_{q_N}^{(N)}. \end{aligned} \quad (116)$$

For the final step, putting (116) into (111) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_\Omega &= \text{tr}(\rho\Omega) = \text{tr}(\rho_\Omega \Lambda_\Omega) \\ &= \text{tr} \left(\rho_\Omega \sum_{q_1, \dots, q_N=1, \dots, 1}^{n_1, \dots, n_N} (\xi_{q_1}^{(1)} \cdots \xi_{q_N}^{(N)}) P_{q_1}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes P_{q_N}^{(N)} \right) \\ &= \sum_{q_1, \dots, q_N=1, \dots, 1}^{n_1, \dots, n_N} (\xi_{q_1}^{(1)} \cdots \xi_{q_N}^{(N)}) \text{tr}(\rho_\Omega P_{q_1}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes P_{q_N}^{(N)}) \\ &\equiv \sum_{\mathbf{q}=1}^{\mathbf{n}} (p_\Omega)_{\mathbf{q}} (\xi_\Omega)_{\mathbf{q}} \equiv \mathbf{p}_\Omega \cdot \boldsymbol{\xi}_\Omega, \end{aligned} \quad (117)$$

which shows that the mean value of any product-form quantum observable can be expressed as a *classical mean*, with classical probabilities

$$(p_\Omega)_{\mathbf{q}} \equiv \text{tr}(\rho_\Omega P_{q_1}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes P_{q_N}^{(N)}) = (\rho_\Omega)_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{q}}, \quad (118)$$

(which are just diagonal elements of the rotated state) weighted by product-form eigenvalues

$$(\xi_\Omega)_{\mathbf{q}} \equiv \xi_{q_1}^{(1)} \cdots \xi_{q_N}^{(N)}, \quad (119)$$

where in (117–119), $\mathbf{n} \equiv (n_1, \dots, n_N)$, $\mathbf{q} \equiv (q_1, \dots, q_N)$, $q_m \in 1, \dots, n_m$, and $\mathbf{1} \equiv (1, \dots, 1_N) = (1, \dots, 1)$.

Furthermore, since (118) is the mean value of *projectors of computational basis states*, the outcomes are unambiguous since there is no superposition in this basis. Also, each outcome clearly corresponds to a particular eigenvalue product that represents it by vector-index \mathbf{q} .

Note that the traditional saying that “we measure eigenvalues” is not accurate language; we measure *occurrences of events* that *correspond to eigenvalues* and that correspondence is what \mathbf{q} describes, while the event itself is the measurement interaction that reports the system to be in computational basis state $P_{q_1}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes P_{q_N}^{(N)}$. This is easily imagined in an experiment where a polarizing beam splitter (PBS) sends a beam of light in one of two directions based on its polarization. Measurements of photons are *counts of electrical pulses* denoting an absorption of one or more photons at a detector at one of the PBS outputs; we do not directly get numerical eigenvalues $+1$ or -1 based on polarization. Rather, the *location* at which the counts were obtained tells us which eigenvalue *corresponds* to that detected event.

Thus, the rotational tomography equation of (117) means that if we want the mean value of Ω as $\Gamma_\Omega = \text{tr}(\rho\Omega)$, we can instead simply measure the mean values of observables $P_{\mathbf{q}} \equiv P_{q_1}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes P_{q_N}^{(N)}$ as $(p_\Omega)_{\mathbf{q}} \equiv \text{tr}(\rho_\Omega P_{\mathbf{q}})$ for the system in the rotated state $\rho_\Omega \equiv \epsilon_\Omega^\dagger \rho \epsilon_\Omega$, and then taking the dot product of those means with their *corresponding eigenvalues* $(\xi_\Omega)_{\mathbf{q}} \equiv \xi_{q_1}^{(1)} \cdots \xi_{q_N}^{(N)}$ yields the value of $\Gamma_\Omega = \text{tr}(\rho\Omega)$. Therefore, operationally, this is simply a matter of finding average detector clicks, and the eigenvalues are never measured directly at all (which is also true in most physical scenarios and theories).

Note that observables $P_{\mathbf{q}} \equiv P_{q_1}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes P_{q_N}^{(N)}$ are *independent of both the input state ρ and the unrotated observable Ω* . The eigenvalue functions $(\xi_\Omega)_{\mathbf{q}} \equiv \xi_{q_1}^{(1)} \cdots \xi_{q_N}^{(N)}$ only depend on the original observable Ω since they are its eigenvalues, and therefore the *original state ρ* only affects the problem through $(p_\Omega)_{\mathbf{q}} \equiv \text{tr}(\rho_\Omega P_{\mathbf{q}})$ which are the *probabilities* of measuring the outcome labeled by \mathbf{q} corresponding to observable $P_{\mathbf{q}} \equiv P_{q_1}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes P_{q_N}^{(N)}$ for the system in the rotated state $\rho_\Omega \equiv \epsilon_\Omega^\dagger \rho \epsilon_\Omega$, and thus these probabilities also depend on the eigenvector matrices of the original observable.

There is much more we could say about this formalism, and in Sec. VID we will extend this to a more general picture to cover all observables with a single classical PDF, while in Sec. VII we will show how to get truly *local* HV models for all observables of any system in any state. But first, we will briefly explore how this rotational tomography relates to effectively nonlocal HV models, thus supporting the eigenvalue hypothesis.

C. Rotational Tomography's Connection to Hidden Variables Supports the Eigenvalue Hypothesis

To see the connection of rotational tomography to HV theory, we recast Bell's mean-value function $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ in discrete form (as in Sec. IIIB or Sec. IV C) and compare it to our results in Sec. VIB. First, $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ becomes

$$P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \sum_\lambda p(\lambda) A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda); \quad \begin{array}{l} A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) \in \pm 1, \\ B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) \in \pm 1, \end{array} \quad (120)$$

where we could change λ to an index as $p(\lambda) \rightarrow p_\lambda$ and $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda), B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) \rightarrow A_\lambda(\mathbf{a}), B_\lambda(\mathbf{b})$, but we keep it as it is for symbolical consistency. Then, comparing (120) to (117) rewritten and adapted to the two-qubit problem (using mode labels 1 and 2 instead of A and B) as

$$\Gamma_\Omega = \sum_{\mathbf{q}=1}^n (p_\Omega)_{\mathbf{q}} \xi_{q_1}^{(1)} \xi_{q_2}^{(2)}; \quad \begin{array}{l} \xi_{q_1}^{(1)} \in \pm 1, \\ \xi_{q_2}^{(2)} \in \pm 1, \end{array} \quad (121)$$

we immediately see the correspondence between (120) and (121) that shows the eigenvalues $\xi_{q_1}^{(1)}$ and $\xi_{q_2}^{(2)}$ of each local observable in (121) to be the analogs of $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ and $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ in (120), which supports (108).

However, one major difference is that in (121), *the eigenvalues are completely independent of detector vectors, and also independent of relative detector angle.*

(The absence of detector-vector dependence in the notation of $\xi_{q_1}^{(1)}$ and $\xi_{q_2}^{(2)}$ is not merely aesthetic; it reflects the fact that there is none, as we will soon see). To see what this observation means, we now take a closer look at the exact form this quantum-derived version takes in the context of Bell's problem.

Letting detector vectors be $\mathbf{a} = (c_{\theta_a}, s_{\theta_a}, 0)$ and $\mathbf{b} = (c_{\theta_b}, s_{\theta_b}, 0)$, where θ_a is the azimuthal angle of \mathbf{a} in the plane perpendicular to particle A 's motion, and θ_b is the azimuthal angle of \mathbf{b} , both relative to the same reference angle, then the local spin operators are

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega^{(1)} &\equiv \sigma_a^{(A)} \equiv \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(A)} \cdot \mathbf{a} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & e^{-i\theta_a} \\ e^{i\theta_a} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \\ \Omega^{(2)} &\equiv \sigma_b^{(B)} \equiv \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(B)} \cdot \mathbf{b} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & e^{-i\theta_b} \\ e^{i\theta_b} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \end{aligned} \quad (122)$$

so the spin-component product $\Omega \equiv \sigma_a^{(A)} \otimes \sigma_b^{(B)}$ is

$$\Omega = \begin{pmatrix} \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & e^{-i(\theta_a+\theta_b)} \\ \cdot & \cdot & e^{-i(\theta_a-\theta_b)} & \cdot \\ \cdot & e^{i(\theta_a-\theta_b)} & \cdot & \cdot \\ e^{i(\theta_a+\theta_b)} & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \end{pmatrix}. \quad (123)$$

Meanwhile, the state is

$$\rho \equiv |\Psi^-\rangle\langle\Psi^-| = \begin{pmatrix} \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} & \cdot \\ \cdot & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \end{pmatrix}, \quad (124)$$

so the mean value of (122) for this state is, from (110),

$$\Gamma_\Omega = \text{tr}(\rho\Omega) = -\cos(\theta_{a,b}) = -\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b} \quad (125)$$

where $\theta_{a,b} \equiv \theta_a - \theta_b$, and we used the fact that $\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b} = c_{\theta_a}c_{\theta_b} + s_{\theta_a}s_{\theta_b} = c_{\theta_a-\theta_b} = \cos(\theta_{a,b})$. Thus, (125) gives us the form of the left side of (121), and now we seek expressions for the quantities on the right side of (121).

First, the eigenvector matrix and eigenvalue matrix of the single-mode observables in (122) are

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{\sigma_a^{(A)}} &\equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ e^{i\theta_a} & -e^{i\theta_a} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Lambda_{\sigma_a^{(A)}} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \xi_1^{(1)} & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_2^{(1)} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \\ \epsilon_{\sigma_b^{(B)}} &\equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ e^{i\theta_b} & -e^{i\theta_b} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Lambda_{\sigma_b^{(B)}} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \xi_1^{(2)} & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_2^{(2)} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \end{aligned} \quad (126)$$

so its eigenvector matrix $\epsilon_\Omega \equiv \epsilon_{\sigma_a^{(A)}} \otimes \epsilon_{\sigma_b^{(B)}}$ is

$$\epsilon_\Omega = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ e^{i\theta_b} & -e^{i\theta_b} & e^{i\theta_b} & -e^{i\theta_b} \\ e^{i\theta_a} & e^{i\theta_a} & -e^{i\theta_a} & -e^{i\theta_a} \\ e^{i(\theta_a+\theta_b)} & -e^{i(\theta_a+\theta_b)} & -e^{i(\theta_a+\theta_b)} & e^{i(\theta_a+\theta_b)} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (127)$$

and its (product-form) eigenvalue matrix $\Lambda_\Omega \equiv \Lambda_{\sigma_a^{(A)}} \otimes \Lambda_{\sigma_b^{(B)}}$ is

$$\Lambda_\Omega = \begin{pmatrix} \xi_1^{(1)} \xi_1^{(2)} & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \xi_1^{(1)} \xi_2^{(2)} & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \xi_2^{(1)} \xi_1^{(2)} & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \xi_2^{(1)} \xi_2^{(2)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (128)$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & -1 & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & -1 & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then, the rotated state $\rho_\Omega \equiv \epsilon_\Omega^\dagger \rho \epsilon_\Omega$ is

$$\rho_\Omega = \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}} & -is_{\theta_{a,b}} & is_{\theta_{a,b}} & -1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}} \\ is_{\theta_{a,b}} & 1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}} & -1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}} & -is_{\theta_{a,b}} \\ -is_{\theta_{a,b}} & -1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}} & 1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}} & is_{\theta_{a,b}} \\ -1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}} & is_{\theta_{a,b}} & -is_{\theta_{a,b}} & 1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (129)$$

(which has the same entanglement as ρ). Therefore the probabilities as defined by the effectively nonlocal HV model by (118) are

$$(p_\Omega)_{\mathbf{q}} \equiv \text{tr}(\rho_\Omega P_{q_1}^{(1)} \otimes P_{q_2}^{(2)}) = \langle q_1 | \langle q_2 | \rho_\Omega | q_1 \rangle | q_2 \rangle = (\rho_\Omega)_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{q}}, \quad (130)$$

which are just the diagonals of the rotated state, so

$$\begin{aligned} (p_\Omega)_{1,1} &= \frac{1}{4}(1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ (p_\Omega)_{1,2} &= \frac{1}{4}(1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ (p_\Omega)_{2,1} &= \frac{1}{4}(1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ (p_\Omega)_{2,2} &= \frac{1}{4}(1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}}), \end{aligned} \quad (131)$$

[which agree with those in (66)]. Then, plugging all of this into the right side of (121) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_\Omega &= \sum_{q_1, q_2=1,1}^{2,2} (p_\Omega)_{q_1, q_2} \xi_{q_1}^{(1)} \xi_{q_2}^{(2)} \\ &= (p_\Omega)_{1,1} \xi_1^{(1)} \xi_1^{(2)} + (p_\Omega)_{1,2} \xi_1^{(1)} \xi_2^{(2)} + (p_\Omega)_{2,1} \xi_2^{(1)} \xi_1^{(2)} + (p_\Omega)_{2,2} \xi_2^{(1)} \xi_2^{(2)} \\ &= (p_\Omega)_{1,1} (+1)(+1) + (p_\Omega)_{1,2} (+1)(-1) + (p_\Omega)_{2,1} (-1)(+1) + (p_\Omega)_{2,2} (-1)(-1) \\ &= (p_\Omega)_{1,1} - (p_\Omega)_{1,2} - (p_\Omega)_{2,1} + (p_\Omega)_{2,2} \\ &= \frac{1}{4}(1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}}) - \frac{1}{4}(1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}}) - \frac{1}{4}(1 + c_{\theta_{a,b}}) + \frac{1}{4}(1 - c_{\theta_{a,b}}) \\ &= \frac{1}{4} - \frac{c_{\theta_{a,b}}}{4} - \frac{1}{4} - \frac{c_{\theta_{a,b}}}{4} - \frac{1}{4} - \frac{c_{\theta_{a,b}}}{4} + \frac{1}{4} - \frac{c_{\theta_{a,b}}}{4} \\ &= -c_{\theta_{a,b}} = -\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}, \end{aligned} \quad (132)$$

which exactly agrees with (125) and shows that the eigenvalue hypothesis is a consistent interpretation of the role of the *values* of the measurement functions $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ and $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ from Bell's model. However, we see that *the eigenvalues themselves do not depend on the detector angles* (either separately or relative), but rather it is the *probability distribution* that changes with relative detector angle, which means that it is the *state* that changes with relative detector angle.

This dependence of the probabilities on relative detector angle makes this a *nonlocal* HV model. However, as we have seen, this nonlocality is merely a side-effect of missing information in an underlying *local* HV model.

Note that similar calculations show that the above nonlocal HV model successfully satisfies (15) as well as (22), which show that it avoids the flaw of Bell's model.

Thus, now that we have given a clear conceptual connection to how quantum mechanics is related to the effectively nonlocal HV theory of Bell's system, we are ready to generalize this to arbitrary states of arbitrary systems, to see how effectively nonlocal HV theories would seem to emerge in all systems.

We will then be ready to construct *local* HV theories with the property of *appearing* to take on these effectively nonlocal forms when certain information is ignored.

D. How to Convert Any Discrete Quantum System to an Effectively Nonlocal HV Model with an Underlying Local HV Model

In Sec. VIA, we showed how to write the mean of any product-form observable in the form of a classical mean in an effectively nonlocal HV model that has the analogous form to the one we found in Sec. IV C which arose from a *local* HV model + ignorance of spin-component magnitudes.

However, that representation leads to a different classical discrete probability distribution for each observable, and it would be preferable to find a *single* probability distribution for all observables.

Therefore, here, we show how to express a Hilbert-Schmidt (HS)-complete set of product-form observables' means in an effectively nonlocal HV model with a single common classical discrete probability distribution for all observables. The HS completeness then also guarantees that any *nonlocal* observables can be represented through appropriate expansions of the product-form observables, so that this representation covers all scenarios.

To find a single classical probability distribution that permits the calculation of the mean of any observable in an effectively nonlocal HV model, we proceed as follows.

Let an HS-complete set of product-form observables be

$$\Omega_{\mathbf{k}} \equiv \Omega_{k_1}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes \Omega_{k_N}^{(N)}; \quad k_m \in 0, \dots, n_m^2 - 1, \quad (133)$$

with the property of HS-orthogonality as

$$\text{tr}(\Omega_{\mathbf{j}}^\dagger \Omega_{\mathbf{k}}) = n \delta_{\mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k}}, \quad (134)$$

with identity element $\Omega_{\mathbf{0}} \equiv I$. Then, for a general Hermitian operator H , it can be expanded as

$$H = \sum_{\mathbf{k}=\mathbf{0}}^{\mathbf{K}} h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \Omega_{\mathbf{k}}, \quad (135)$$

where $\mathbf{K} \equiv (K_1, \dots, K_N)$ with $K_m \equiv n_m^2 - 1$, and

$$h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} = \frac{1}{n} \text{tr}(\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger H). \quad (136)$$

So the mean value of a general Hermitian operator H of a system in state ρ is, from (135),

$$\langle H \rangle_\rho \equiv \text{tr}(\rho H) = \sum_{\mathbf{k}=\mathbf{0}}^{\mathbf{K}} h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \text{tr}(\rho \Omega_{\mathbf{k}}). \quad (137)$$

Since we want to see the eigenvalues of observables explicitly, we expand the basis observables as

$$\Omega_{\mathbf{k}} = \epsilon_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \Lambda_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \epsilon_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}^\dagger, \quad (138)$$

where $\epsilon_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}$ is the unitary eigenvector matrix of $\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}$, and its eigenvalue matrix is

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} &= \Lambda_{\Omega_{k_1}^{(1)}} \otimes \cdots \otimes \Lambda_{\Omega_{k_N}^{(N)}} \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{n}} [(\xi_{\Omega_{k_1}^{(1)}}^{(1)})_{q_1} \cdots (\xi_{\Omega_{k_N}^{(N)}}^{(N)})_{q_N}] P_{q_1}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes P_{q_N}^{(N)} \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{q}=1}^{\mathbf{n}} (\xi_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}^{\mathbf{q}}) P_{\mathbf{q}}, \end{aligned} \quad (139)$$

where operator eigenvalues and computational basis projectors are

$$\begin{aligned} (\xi_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}})_{\mathbf{q}} &\equiv (\xi_{\Omega_{k_1}^{(1)}}^{(1)})_{q_1} \cdots (\xi_{\Omega_{k_N}^{(N)}}^{(N)})_{q_N}; \\ P_{\mathbf{q}} &\equiv P_{q_1}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes P_{q_N}^{(N)}; \quad P_{q_m}^{(m)} \equiv |q_m^{(m)}\rangle \langle q_m^{(m)}|. \end{aligned} \quad (140)$$

So then putting (139) into (138) gives

$$\Omega_{\mathbf{k}} = \sum_{\mathbf{q}=1}^{\mathbf{n}} (\xi_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}})_{\mathbf{q}} \epsilon_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} P_{\mathbf{q}} \epsilon_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}^\dagger, \quad (141)$$

and putting (141) into (137) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \langle H \rangle_\rho &= \sum_{\mathbf{k}=\mathbf{0}}^{\mathbf{K}} \sum_{\mathbf{q}=1}^{\mathbf{n}} \frac{1}{n^2} \text{tr}(\rho \epsilon_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} P_{\mathbf{q}} \epsilon_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}^\dagger) n^2 h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} (\xi_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}})_{\mathbf{q}} \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{k}=\mathbf{0}}^{\mathbf{K}} \sum_{\mathbf{q}=1}^{\mathbf{n}} p'_{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q})} \xi'_{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q})} \\ &\equiv \mathbf{p}' \cdot \boldsymbol{\xi}', \end{aligned} \quad (142)$$

from which we obtain n^3 probabilities as elements of \mathbf{p}' ,

$$p'_{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q})} \equiv \frac{1}{n^2} \text{tr}(\rho \epsilon_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} P_{\mathbf{q}} \epsilon_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}^\dagger), \quad (143)$$

and n^3 weighted eigenvalues as elements of $\boldsymbol{\xi}'$,

$$\xi'_{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q})} \equiv n^2 h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} (\xi_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}})_{\mathbf{q}} = n \text{tr}(\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger H) (\xi_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}})_{\mathbf{q}}, \quad (144)$$

where we used $h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} = \frac{1}{n} \text{tr}(\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger H)$ from (136).

Thus, *the mean of any observable H for a physical system in any discrete quantum state ρ can be expressed as a classical discrete mean with a single classical discrete probability distribution with the probabilities of (143).*

Granted, this set of probabilities has n^3 elements instead of just n , but those elements are common to the entire family of infinitely many observables.

For measurements, we can convert (143) to the rotated state for each of the *basis* observables as

$$p'_{(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q})} \equiv \frac{1}{n^2} \text{tr}(\epsilon_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}^\dagger \rho \epsilon_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} P_{\mathbf{q}}) = \frac{1}{n^2} \text{tr}(\rho_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} P_{\mathbf{q}}) = \frac{1}{n^2} (\rho_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}})_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{q}}, \quad (145)$$

with n^2 rotated states

$$\rho_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \equiv \epsilon_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}^\dagger \rho \epsilon_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}, \quad (146)$$

and while the eigenvalues must be weighted as in (144), we have nevertheless found a *single* classical probability distribution that describes the mean of all observables, which is a truly *classical* way to express mean values.

Thus, this gives us a universal way to construct the effectively nonlocal HV model for every possible system in every possible state for every possible observable, providing a classical probability distribution in terms of linear combinations of mean values of product observables (which qualify as Bloch-vector components since they are mean values of the HS complete product basis).

However, all of this also suggests how to find the underlying *local* HV model; if we can just find an appropriate set of *local* measurement functions *whose product averages yield the Bloch-vector components*, then we will have achieved our local HV model.

We propose this idea more formally in Sec. VI E, and then present a working solution for it in Sec. VII as the culminating result of this paper.

E. Hypothesis: Universal Admission of Local Hidden-Variable Models

Now that we have shown in Sec. VI D that any discrete quantum system can have any observable represented as a classical average with a single common classical probability distribution, and that this form is entirely analogous to the effectively nonlocal HV model we got by discarding information from our successful local HV model as in Sec. IV C, we are poised to make a radical hypothesis:

Universal Local HV Hypothesis: *All quantum systems admit a local HV model that can, in principle, predict all physical results, both in terms of mean values of observables and in terms of predicting exactly when all particular outcomes of measurements will happen, given initial conditions of the hidden variables. If certain information is unknown, such a local HV model plus that ignorance leads to an effectively nonlocal HV model that is derivable from quantum mechanics in the way shown in Sec. VI D.*

(147)

This existence part of local HV models of this hypothesis is more easily proven than it seems; Sec. VII (next) proves this by example for all multipartite quantum systems, and proves that such HV models are truly local.

However, there is not just one way to construct such a local HV model – there appear to be infinitely many variations that could do the job, each one with a generally different deterministic prediction of when measurement results will happen (and yet all of which are fully compatible with QM).

But in all cases, we can always recover the effectively nonlocal HV models by ignoring some information from the measurement functions.

Therefore, the universal local HV hypothesis is actually proven to be *valid* in Sec. VII, with the caveat that out of the infinite number of possible different local HV models, the examples we give are probably not the ones whose deterministic solutions correspond to this particular universe.

However, the fact that such solutions are even possible is something that Bell and others have thought to be impossible until now, and their existence shows that in principle, it might eventually be possible to experimentally determine the particular local HV model that corresponds to a given physical system (if any do at all).

VII. LOCAL HV MODELS FOR ALL SYSTEMS

Here we present the most important result of this paper: proof by example that it is possible to construct truly *local* HV models for all states of all multipartite discrete quantum systems.

The locality of this model is due to its uniform PDF *and* the fact that each mode's measurement function only depends on its own local detector parameters. Any correlations in the system arise from some initial preparation involving synchronizations between the multiple particles in a situation where they are all locally grouped together before flying apart. In this sense, the initial Bloch components describe things like initial phase offsets and/or amplitudes in deterministic equations of motion.

First, in Sec. VII A we present one possible general description for local HV models for all multipartite systems. Then in Sec. VII B, we demonstrate the agreement of such models with QM in a two-qubit example, followed by many examples in many systems in Sec. VII D, while Sec. VII C shows how to model quantization in multipartite systems with two-type transmission. Then in Sec. VII E, we discuss how to incorporate time evolution.

A. A Working Local HV Model for All Multipartite Discrete Systems

For any N -mode discrete system for $N \geq 1$, a general *local measurement function* exists for each mode as

$$\begin{aligned} A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)} &\equiv A^{(m)}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}^{(m)}, \lambda) \equiv \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^{(m)} \cdot \mathbf{A}^{(m)}(\lambda) \\ &\equiv \sum_{k_m=0}^{n_m^2-1} a_{k_m}^{(m)} A_{k_m}^{(m)}(\lambda), \end{aligned} \quad (148)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}^{(m)}$ is an n_m^2 -dimensional unit vector with components $a_{k_m}^{(m)}$ that can be parameterized with Schläfli's hyperspherical coordinates [20, 21], and whose angles of nonzero index correspond to some physical parameters of the local detector orientation (such as phase shifters in an N -mode interferometer), while the 0-index angle describes how much of the m -mode identity operation is represented in this observable's measurement function.

$\mathbf{A}^{(m)}(\lambda)$ is a vector of principal-direction measurement functions for mode m , the components of which can be

modeled as

$$\begin{aligned} A_{k_m}^{(m)}(\lambda) &\equiv \delta_{N,1} \Gamma_{k_1} (1 + c_{\tilde{\omega}_{k_1}^{(1)}} \lambda + \tilde{\phi}_{k_1}^{(1)}) + \sum_{\mathbf{k}_{\overline{m}}=0}^{\mathbf{K}_{\overline{m}}} X_{\mathbf{k}}^{(m)}(\lambda) \\ &= \delta_{N,1} \Gamma_{k_1} (1 + c_{\tilde{\omega}_{k_1}^{(1)}} \lambda + \tilde{\phi}_{k_1}^{(1)}) \\ &\quad + \sum_{k_1=0}^{n_1^2-1} \cdots \sum_{k_{m-1}=0}^{n_{m-1}^2-1} \sum_{k_{m+1}=0}^{n_{m+1}^2-1} \cdots \sum_{k_N=0}^{n_N^2-1} X_{k_1, \dots, k_N}^{(m)}(\lambda), \end{aligned} \quad (149)$$

where $\Gamma_{\mathbf{k}} \equiv \Gamma_{k_1, \dots, k_N}$ (for $k_m \in 0, \dots, n_m^2 - 1$ and $m \in 1, \dots, N$) are *unitized* Bloch-vector components which are mean values of some *rescaled* HS-complete product basis $\{\frac{1}{\sqrt{n-1}} \nu_{\mathbf{k}}\}$, where $\text{tr}(\nu_{\mathbf{j}} \nu_{\mathbf{k}}) = n \delta_{\mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k}}$, similar to (134), so the unitization factor $\frac{1}{\sqrt{n-1}}$ enters the mean as

$$\Gamma_{\mathbf{k} \neq \mathbf{0}} \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{n-1}} \text{tr}(\rho \nu_{\mathbf{k}}), \quad (150)$$

where *unitization* is the property of a Bloch vector having HS magnitude $|\Gamma| = 1$ iff ρ is pure, and is not the same concept as normalization {see (App. K of [19]) for more details}. The $X_{\mathbf{k}}^{(m)}(\lambda)$ are *correlation measurement components* (which only carry information about correlations imparted by the initial synchronization during local creation of the system, such as initially synchronized rotations and relative phase shifts), and can be given by

$$\begin{aligned} X_{\mathbf{k}}^{(m)}(\lambda) &\equiv 2^{\frac{N-1}{N}} \cos(\omega_{\mathbf{k}}^{(m)} \lambda + \phi_{\mathbf{k}}^{(m)}); \\ \phi_{\mathbf{k}}^{(m)} &\equiv \frac{1}{N} \text{acos} \left[\frac{1}{1 + \delta_{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{0}} (\sqrt{n-1})} \Gamma_{\mathbf{k}} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (151)$$

(see App. A) where angular frequencies for each \mathbf{k} satisfy

$$\sum_{m=1}^N \omega_{\mathbf{k}}^{(m)} = 0 \quad \text{and each } \tilde{\omega}_{k_1}^{(1)} \text{ is unique,} \quad (152)$$

where $\omega_{\mathbf{k}}^{(m)} \equiv \frac{2\pi}{L} \mu_{\mathbf{k}}^{(m)}$ and $\tilde{\omega}_{k_1}^{(1)} \equiv \frac{2\pi}{L} \tilde{\mu}_{k_1}^{(1)}$ for some nonzero integers $\mu_{\mathbf{k}}^{(m)}$ and $\tilde{\mu}_{k_1}^{(1)}$ and fundamental HV period L , and furthermore, with the constraint that frequency sets belonging to different \mathbf{k} cannot sum to 0 with any combinations of weights ± 1 . Note also that $\Gamma_{\mathbf{0}} \equiv 1$.

DC offsets Γ_{k_1} and *unipartite* angular frequencies $\tilde{\omega}_{k_1}^{(1)}$ and phase shifts $\tilde{\phi}_{k_1}^{(1)}$ are not necessary in strictly multipartite systems, but are included here so that when $N = 1$ (a unipartite system), we can still get a dynamical deterministic function for the measurement operators. For any QM expectation value, simply substitute mean values of $A_{k_1}^{(1)}(\lambda) \cdots A_{k_N}^{(N)}(\lambda)$ from (149) wherever their corresponding Bloch-vector components $\Gamma_{\mathbf{k}}$ appear.

(Note that this particular model and its frequency restrictions are not necessary conditions, but are instead merely *convenient* conditions for the purpose of making our constructions easy to demonstrate our main point that such models are at all possible.) A recursive formula that generates such sets of frequencies is:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\omega}_{\mathbf{k}} &\equiv \frac{1}{\omega} (\omega_{\mathbf{k}}^{(1)}, \dots, \omega_{\mathbf{k}}^{(N)}) \\ &= M_{\mathbf{k}}(1, \dots, 1, -(N-1)) \\ &\quad + (1, \dots, N-1, -\frac{N(N-1)}{2}); \\ M_{\mathbf{k} \neq \mathbf{0}} &\equiv \|\hat{\omega}_{\mathbf{k}_{\text{previous}}}\|_1 - \frac{1}{\omega} |\omega_{\mathbf{k}_{\text{previous}}}^{(1)}|^2 \\ &= N(N-1) + (2N-3)M_{\mathbf{k}_{\text{previous}}} - 1; \\ M_{\mathbf{0}} &\equiv 0, \end{aligned} \quad (153)$$

where $\mathbf{k} = \mathbf{0}$ is used as the first vector index in the set. It is then true that

$$\begin{aligned} \langle A_{k_1}^{(1)} \cdots A_{k_N}^{(N)} \rangle &\equiv \int_0^L \frac{1}{L} A_{k_1}^{(1)}(\lambda) \cdots A_{k_N}^{(N)}(\lambda) d\lambda \\ &= \begin{cases} \Gamma_{\mathbf{k}}; & \mathbf{k} \neq \mathbf{0} \\ \frac{\Gamma_{\mathbf{0}}}{\sqrt{n-1}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n-1}}; & \mathbf{k} = \mathbf{0}, \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (154)$$

so that the mean values of principal-direction observables are completely reproduced by these principal-direction measurement functions, where we used the fact that for periodic functions $f(\lambda)$ of period L averaged over interval $\mathcal{L} \gg L$, $\frac{1}{\mathcal{L}} \int_0^{\mathcal{L}} f(\lambda) d\lambda \approx \frac{1}{L} \int_0^L f(\lambda) d\lambda$. (The need for a separate case in (154) can be avoided if we rescale the $\nu_{\mathbf{0}}$ identity operator, but it is often more useful to leave it as the identity as we have). Then, for any local detector vectors, the measurement functions of (148) give the mean values of products of observables as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle A_{a^{(1)}}^{(1)} \cdots A_{a^{(N)}}^{(N)} \rangle &\equiv \int_0^L \frac{1}{L} A^{(1)}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}^{(1)}, \lambda) \cdots A^{(N)}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}^{(N)}, \lambda) d\lambda \\ &= \langle \Omega_{a^{(1)}}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes \Omega_{a^{(N)}}^{(N)} \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (155)$$

which shows that even though the observables only depend on their own local detector vectors, the fact that the initial state represents the correlations arising from initial local synchronizations in the creation of the system allows this mean over λ to yield the correct quantum-mechanical average of any product observable [indicated by what it yields in line 2 of (155), where $\Omega_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}$ is the quantum-mechanical generalized ‘‘spin-component operator’’ for mode m , meaning a local-unitarily transformed rescaled HS-complete basis operator].

Note that in this model, we use the paradigm that an N -mode product observable is a product of N functions, and if any represent the identity, those functions have a subscript of 0 such as $\langle A_3^{(1)} A_0^{(2)} A_2^{(3)} \rangle$. While it is possible to use a different convention that would allow this to be written as $\langle A_3^{(1)} A_2^{(3)} \rangle$, the N -factor product method has a much simpler form, so we use it here for clarity.

B. Example: Local HV Model for Two Qubits

To see how this works, first we need to see what QM predicts. If each detector has its own detector vector as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{a} &= s_{\chi_a} c_{\theta_a} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_1 + s_{\chi_a} s_{\theta_a} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_2 + c_{\chi_a} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_3, \\ \mathbf{b} &= s_{\chi_b} c_{\theta_b} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_1 + s_{\chi_b} s_{\theta_b} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_2 + c_{\chi_b} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_3, \end{aligned} \quad (156)$$

where $\chi_a, \chi_b \in [0, \pi]$ are polar angles and $\theta_a, \theta_b \in [0, 2\pi)$ are azimuthal angles in the plane perpendicular to the 3-axis, then we can define *augmented detector vectors*,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{a}} &\equiv \tilde{\mathbf{a}}^{(1)} \equiv c_{\eta_a} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 + s_{\eta_a} \mathbf{a} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{b}} &\equiv \tilde{\mathbf{b}}^{(2)} \equiv c_{\eta_b} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 + s_{\eta_b} \mathbf{b}, \end{aligned} \quad (157)$$

where $\eta_a, \eta_b \in [0, 2\pi)$ are parameters describing how much we wish to ignore a given system (i.e. $\eta_a \in \{0, \pi\}$ means fully ignoring mode A , while $\eta_a = \frac{\pi}{2}$ means fully considering its spin-component product).

If we then define the *augmented Pauli vector* $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \equiv (\sigma_0, \sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3)$, we get the *augmented spin-component operators* for each mode as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\sigma}_a^{(A)} &\equiv \tilde{\mathbf{a}} \cdot \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \begin{pmatrix} c_{\eta_a} + s_{\eta_a} c_{\chi_a} & s_{\eta_a} s_{\chi_a} e^{-i\theta_a} \\ s_{\eta_a} s_{\chi_a} e^{i\theta_a} & c_{\eta_a} - s_{\eta_a} c_{\chi_a} \end{pmatrix} \\ \tilde{\sigma}_b^{(B)} &\equiv \tilde{\mathbf{b}} \cdot \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \begin{pmatrix} c_{\eta_b} + s_{\eta_b} c_{\chi_b} & s_{\eta_b} s_{\chi_b} e^{-i\theta_b} \\ s_{\eta_b} s_{\chi_b} e^{i\theta_b} & c_{\eta_b} - s_{\eta_b} c_{\chi_b} \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (158)$$

If we then define the rescaled spin-product observables,

$$\Omega \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \tilde{\sigma}_a^{(A)} \otimes \tilde{\sigma}_b^{(B)} \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \tilde{\sigma}_a \tilde{\sigma}_b, \quad (159)$$

where $\tilde{\sigma}_a \equiv \tilde{\sigma}_a^{(A)} \otimes I^{(B)}$ and $\tilde{\sigma}_b \equiv I^{(A)} \otimes \tilde{\sigma}_b^{(B)}$, then we obtain the QM spin-component product average,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \tilde{\sigma}_a \tilde{\sigma}_b \rangle &= \text{tr}(\rho \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \tilde{\sigma}_a \tilde{\sigma}_b) = \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \Gamma_{0,0} c_{\eta_a} c_{\eta_b} + \Gamma_{0,3} c_{\eta_a} s_{\eta_b} c_{\chi_b} + \Gamma_{3,0} s_{\eta_a} c_{\chi_a} c_{\eta_b} + \Gamma_{3,3} s_{\eta_a} c_{\chi_a} s_{\eta_b} c_{\chi_b} \\ &+ s_{\eta_b} s_{\chi_b} (c_{\eta_a} [\Gamma_{0,1} c_{\theta_b} + \Gamma_{0,2} s_{\theta_b}] + s_{\eta_a} c_{\chi_a} [\Gamma_{3,1} c_{\theta_b} + \Gamma_{3,2} s_{\theta_b}]) \\ &+ s_{\eta_a} s_{\chi_a} (c_{\eta_b} [\Gamma_{1,0} c_{\theta_a} + \Gamma_{2,0} s_{\theta_a}] + s_{\eta_b} c_{\chi_b} [\Gamma_{1,3} c_{\theta_a} + \Gamma_{2,3} s_{\theta_a}]) \\ &+ s_{\eta_a} s_{\chi_a} s_{\eta_b} s_{\chi_b} (\Gamma_{1,1} c_{\theta_a} c_{\theta_b} + \Gamma_{1,2} c_{\theta_a} s_{\theta_b} + \Gamma_{2,1} s_{\theta_a} c_{\theta_b} + \Gamma_{2,2} s_{\theta_a} s_{\theta_b}), \end{aligned} \quad (160)$$

where the unitized Bloch-vector components Γ_{k_1, k_2} were converted from the density-matrix elements using

$$\Gamma_{\mathbf{k} \neq \mathbf{0}} \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{n-1}} \text{tr}(\rho \nu_{\mathbf{k}}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n-1}} \sum_{c=1}^n \sum_{d=1}^n \rho_{c,d} (\nu_{\mathbf{k}})_{d,c}, \quad (161)$$

where $\nu_{\mathbf{k}} \equiv \nu_{k_1}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes \nu_{k_N}^{(N)}$ is the rescaled Gell-Mann basis as $\nu_0^{(m)} \equiv \lambda_0^{(m)} \equiv I^{(m)}$ and $\nu_{k_m}^{(m)} \equiv \sqrt{\frac{n-m}{2}} \lambda_{k_m}^{(m)}$ for $k_m \in 1, \dots, n_m - 1$, where $\lambda_{k_m}^{(m)}$ is the k_m th Gell-Mann matrix [14, 19, 22, 23].

Thus, (160) gives the QM result. Now the question is: *can we find a classical average of a product of two functions of different sets of local detector angles that yields the same form as (160)?* The answer is *yes*, with one possible way given in Sec. VII A as we now show.

From (148), the proposed functions have the form (suppressing the HV dependence on λ in the $A_{k_m}^{(m)}$ functions)

$$\begin{aligned} A_a^{(1)} &\equiv A^{(1)}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}, \lambda) \equiv A^{(1)}(\theta_a, \chi_a, \eta_a, \lambda) \\ &= c_{\eta_a} A_0^{(1)} + s_{\eta_a} s_{\chi_a} c_{\theta_a} A_1^{(1)} + s_{\eta_a} s_{\chi_a} s_{\theta_a} A_2^{(1)} + s_{\eta_a} c_{\chi_a} A_3^{(1)} \\ A_b^{(2)} &\equiv A^{(2)}(\tilde{\mathbf{b}}, \lambda) \equiv A^{(2)}(\theta_b, \chi_b, \eta_b, \lambda) \\ &= c_{\eta_b} A_0^{(2)} + s_{\eta_b} s_{\chi_b} c_{\theta_b} A_1^{(2)} + s_{\eta_b} s_{\chi_b} s_{\theta_b} A_2^{(2)} + s_{\eta_b} c_{\chi_b} A_3^{(2)}, \end{aligned} \quad (162)$$

and the mean value of the product of these functions is

$$\begin{aligned} \langle A_a^{(1)} A_b^{(2)} \rangle &= \\ &= \langle A_0^{(1)} A_0^{(2)} \rangle c_{\eta_a} c_{\eta_b} + \langle A_0^{(1)} A_3^{(2)} \rangle c_{\eta_a} s_{\eta_b} c_{\chi_b} + \langle A_3^{(1)} A_0^{(2)} \rangle s_{\eta_a} c_{\chi_a} c_{\eta_b} + \langle A_3^{(1)} A_3^{(2)} \rangle s_{\eta_a} c_{\chi_a} s_{\eta_b} c_{\chi_b} \\ &+ s_{\eta_b} s_{\chi_b} (c_{\eta_a} [(A_0^{(1)} A_1^{(2)}) c_{\theta_b} + (A_0^{(1)} A_2^{(2)}) s_{\theta_b}] + s_{\eta_a} c_{\chi_a} [(A_3^{(1)} A_1^{(2)}) c_{\theta_b} + (A_3^{(1)} A_2^{(2)}) s_{\theta_b}]) \\ &+ s_{\eta_a} s_{\chi_a} (c_{\eta_b} [(A_1^{(1)} A_0^{(2)}) c_{\theta_a} + (A_2^{(1)} A_0^{(2)}) s_{\theta_a}] + s_{\eta_b} c_{\chi_b} [(A_1^{(1)} A_3^{(2)}) c_{\theta_a} + (A_2^{(1)} A_3^{(2)}) s_{\theta_a}]) \\ &+ s_{\eta_a} s_{\chi_a} s_{\eta_b} s_{\chi_b} (\langle A_1^{(1)} A_1^{(2)} \rangle c_{\theta_a} c_{\theta_b} + \langle A_1^{(1)} A_2^{(2)} \rangle c_{\theta_a} s_{\theta_b} + \langle A_2^{(1)} A_1^{(2)} \rangle s_{\theta_a} c_{\theta_b} + \langle A_2^{(1)} A_2^{(2)} \rangle s_{\theta_a} s_{\theta_b}), \end{aligned} \quad (163)$$

which has exactly the same form as the QM version in (160), but with means of products of $A_{k_m}^{(m)}$ in place of $\Gamma_{\mathbf{k}}$.

Notice that the measurement functions in (162) are indeed local since the coefficients only depend on their own *local* detector vectors, while the principal-direction functions $A_{k_m}^{(m)}$ only depend on initial phase-shift correlations via the Bloch-vector components in (151).

These principal-direction functions are then given by (149) as

$$\begin{aligned}
A_0^{(1)}(\lambda) &\equiv X_{0,0}^{(1)}(\lambda) + X_{0,1}^{(1)}(\lambda) + X_{0,2}^{(1)}(\lambda) + X_{0,3}^{(1)}(\lambda) \\
A_1^{(1)}(\lambda) &\equiv X_{1,0}^{(1)}(\lambda) + X_{1,1}^{(1)}(\lambda) + X_{1,2}^{(1)}(\lambda) + X_{1,3}^{(1)}(\lambda) \\
A_2^{(1)}(\lambda) &\equiv X_{2,0}^{(1)}(\lambda) + X_{2,1}^{(1)}(\lambda) + X_{2,2}^{(1)}(\lambda) + X_{2,3}^{(1)}(\lambda) \\
A_3^{(1)}(\lambda) &\equiv X_{3,0}^{(1)}(\lambda) + X_{3,1}^{(1)}(\lambda) + X_{3,2}^{(1)}(\lambda) + X_{3,3}^{(1)}(\lambda) \\
A_0^{(2)}(\lambda) &\equiv X_{0,0}^{(2)}(\lambda) + X_{1,0}^{(2)}(\lambda) + X_{2,0}^{(2)}(\lambda) + X_{3,0}^{(2)}(\lambda) \\
A_1^{(2)}(\lambda) &\equiv X_{0,1}^{(2)}(\lambda) + X_{1,1}^{(2)}(\lambda) + X_{2,1}^{(2)}(\lambda) + X_{3,1}^{(2)}(\lambda) \\
A_2^{(2)}(\lambda) &\equiv X_{0,2}^{(2)}(\lambda) + X_{1,2}^{(2)}(\lambda) + X_{2,2}^{(2)}(\lambda) + X_{3,2}^{(2)}(\lambda) \\
A_3^{(2)}(\lambda) &\equiv X_{0,3}^{(2)}(\lambda) + X_{1,3}^{(2)}(\lambda) + X_{2,3}^{(2)}(\lambda) + X_{3,3}^{(2)}(\lambda),
\end{aligned} \tag{164}$$

where the correlation measurement functions $X_{k_1, k_2}^{(m)}(\lambda)$ are given explicitly by (151) with angular frequencies,

$$\begin{aligned}
\omega_{0,0} &= \omega(1, -1), & \omega_{2,0} &= \omega(9, -9), \\
\omega_{0,1} &= \omega(2, -2), & \omega_{2,1} &= \omega(10, -10), \\
\omega_{0,2} &= \omega(3, -3), & \omega_{2,2} &= \omega(11, -11), \\
\omega_{0,3} &= \omega(4, -4), & \omega_{2,3} &= \omega(12, -12), \\
\omega_{1,0} &= \omega(5, -5), & \omega_{3,0} &= \omega(13, -13), \\
\omega_{1,1} &= \omega(6, -6), & \omega_{3,1} &= \omega(14, -14), \\
\omega_{1,2} &= \omega(7, -7), & \omega_{3,2} &= \omega(15, -15), \\
\omega_{1,3} &= \omega(8, -8), & \omega_{3,3} &= \omega(16, -16).
\end{aligned} \tag{165}$$

It is then true that

$$\langle A_{k_1}^{(1)} A_{k_2}^{(2)} \rangle = \int_0^L \frac{1}{L} A_{k_1}^{(1)} A_{k_2}^{(2)} d\lambda = \begin{cases} \Gamma_{\mathbf{k}}; & \mathbf{k} \neq \mathbf{0} \\ \frac{\Gamma_{\mathbf{0}}}{\sqrt{n-1}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}; & \mathbf{k} = \mathbf{0}, \end{cases} \tag{166}$$

which, when put into (163) [or putting (164) into (162) and putting that into (163)] yields

$$\langle A_a^{(1)} A_b^{(2)} \rangle = \int_0^L \frac{1}{L} A^{(1)}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}, \lambda) A^{(2)}(\tilde{\mathbf{b}}, \lambda) d\lambda = \langle \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \tilde{\sigma}_a \tilde{\sigma}_b \rangle, \tag{167}$$

which shows that our *local* classical product average produces exactly the same mean values as QM. Furthermore, not only are the two measurement functions independent of each other's detector angles, but the PDF of the hidden variable $p(\lambda) \equiv \frac{1}{L}$ is *uniform* and therefore completely independent of either set of detector angles, which preserves the locality of these measurement functions.

From the above argument, comparing (163) to (160) shows that to check whether this works, we merely need to verify that the mean values in (163) equal the corresponding Bloch-vector components in (160); in other words, to verify (167) for a given state, it is sufficient to check that (166) holds true, since we already know the general mean value has the correct form for all possible detector-angle combinations.

Figure 6 shows numerical checks of (166) for an arbitrary quantum state, and a check of (167) (inset) to demonstrate of the validity of this local HV model.

FIG. 6: (color online) Bar graph comparing product means of local HV principal-direction measurement functions of (164) to the QM Bloch-vector components to check (166) for an arbitrary entangled quantum mixed state of two qubits. Inset: check of (167) by comparing the local HV product mean for arbitrary-direction measurement functions to the QM observable mean, letting each detector's augmented detector vector be arbitrary. Agreement is always achieved (tested over 10^4 different states, not shown here). This is an excellent demonstration that there exist local HV models that agree with QM.

FIG. 7: (color online) Plot of the principal-direction measurement functions from (164) vs. λ for the same arbitrary state as Fig. 6 to show what they look like. For two qubits, the sign of each $A_{km}^{(m)}$ determines the quantum measurement values at any λ when the augmented detector vectors $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{b}}$ from (157) are implemented physically as local-unitary operations.

The local principal-direction measurement functions of (164) are plotted in Fig. 7. In principle, the *signs* of these functions determine the quantum measurement values at each λ , but to properly model quantization, the two-type transmission model is useful.

Therefore, to achieve fully deterministic functions *and* incorporate quantization, we now generalize the two-type transmission model of Sec. IV B to multipartite systems.

C. Accounting for Quantization in Multipartite Local HV Models with Two-Type Transmission

Recalling the principal-direction measurement functions $A_{k_m}^{(m)}(\lambda)$ of (149), note that each one has $n_{\bar{m}} \equiv \frac{n}{n_m}$ terms, where each term is a correlation measurement function $X_{k_m}^{(m)}(\lambda)$ from (151) which is a cosine with amplitude $2^{\frac{k-1}{N}}$. Therefore, each $A_{k_m}^{(m)}(\lambda)$ has a range of $A_{k_m}^{(m)}(\lambda) \in n_{\bar{m}}^2 2^{\frac{N-1}{N} + \delta_{N,1}} [-1, 1]$ (note: $n_{\bar{m}} = 1$ if $N = 1$).

Then, since the mode- m arbitrary-direction measurement functions $A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)$ of (148) [where we suppress the dependence on local detector vector $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}^{(m)}$] are merely dot products of unit vector $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}^{(m)}$ with the vector whose elements are $A_{k_m}^{(m)}(\lambda)$, the range of $A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)$ is

$$A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda) \in n_{\bar{m}}^2 2^{\frac{N-1}{N} + \delta_{N,1}} [-1, 1]. \quad (168)$$

In the $\{\nu_{\mathbf{k}}\}$ basis, eigenvalues only take up to three distinct values; one for each *sign* and 0, with each non-negative type being degenerate in general. Since local-unitary operations preserve those eigenvalues, they persist for the arbitrary direction measurement functions for general product observables. Therefore our quantization map only needs to depend on the *sign* of normalized measurement functions, which can then be further divided for degeneracy to get *quantized measurement functions* as

$$A_{a^{(m)}, Q}^{(m)}(\lambda) \equiv \text{map}[A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)] \equiv \begin{cases} \xi_{q_+}^{(m)}; & \hat{A}_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda) \in [\frac{n_+ - q_+}{n_+}, \frac{n_+ - q_+ + 1}{n_+}] \\ \xi_{n_+ + q_0}^{(m)}; & \hat{A}_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda) = 0; \text{ iff } n_0 \neq 0 \\ \xi_{n_+ + n_0 + q_-}^{(m)}; & \hat{A}_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda) \in [-\frac{q_-}{n_-}, -\frac{q_- - 1}{n_-}] \end{cases} \quad (169)$$

s.t. $\xi_q^{(m)} \equiv (\xi_{\Omega^{(m)}}^{(m)})_q$, $\hat{A}_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda) \equiv A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda) / (n_{\bar{m}}^2 2^{\frac{N-1}{N} + \delta_{N,1}})$, and local observables' eigenvalues obey $\xi_1^{(m)} \geq \dots \geq \xi_{n_m}^{(m)}$ with numbers of each type of sign of eigenvalue for a given local observable denoted as n_+ , n_0 , and $n_- = n_m - n_+ - n_0$, with eigenvalue indices $q_+ \in 1, \dots, n_+$, $q_0 \in 1, \dots, n_0$, and $q_- \in 1, \dots, n_-$, and in the top case of (169), the lower limit becomes exclusive when $n_0 \neq 0$.

Implied in this map is that a particular general index $q \in 1, \dots, n_m$ indicates *which mode- m computational basis state $|q^{(m)}\rangle$* (counting from 1) would happen at that λ ; either $|(q_+)^{(m)}\rangle$, $|(n_+ + q_0)^{(m)}\rangle$, or $|(n_+ + n_0 + q_-)^{(m)}\rangle$. Again, this is because the event of which collapse happens is the true physical observable, while the eigenvalue is merely part of its mathematical representation; specifying the projected outcome $|q^{(m)}\rangle$ is necessary to distinguish events in the case of degenerate eigenvalues.

Note that since there is no degeneracy in the negative eigenvalue, we technically do not need to partition the negative values of $\hat{A}_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)$ in (169), but we keep it general here in case different basis operators are used.

Then, using the map of (169), if we adopt a two-type transmission model similar to that in Sec. IV B, we can expand the measurement functions to define the *classical measurement functions* of type-1 transmission as

$$\begin{aligned} A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda) &= n_{\bar{m}}^2 2^{\frac{N-1}{N} + \delta_{N,1}} \frac{|A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)| \text{sgn}[A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)]}{n_{\bar{m}}^2 2^{\frac{N-1}{N} + \delta_{N,1}} \frac{|\xi_q^{(m)}|}{|\xi_q^{(m)} + \delta_{\xi_q^{(m)}, 0}|}} \\ &= n_{\bar{m}}^2 2^{\frac{N-1}{N} + \delta_{N,1}} \frac{|A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)|}{n_{\bar{m}}^2 2^{\frac{N-1}{N} + \delta_{N,1}} \frac{\xi_q^{(m)}}{|\xi_q^{(m)} + \delta_{\xi_q^{(m)}, 0}|}} \\ &= \frac{|A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)|}{n_{\bar{m}}^2 2^{\frac{N-1}{N} + \delta_{N,1}} \frac{\text{map}[A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)]}{|\text{map}[A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)] + \delta_{\text{map}[A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)], 0}|}}, \end{aligned} \quad (170)$$

where $\xi_q^{(m)} \equiv (\xi_{\Omega^{(m)}}^{(m)})_q$ and $\text{sgn}[A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)] = \text{sgn}[\xi_q^{(m)}]$ was used by (169). $A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}$ Then (170) takes three useful forms;

$$\begin{aligned} A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda) &= F_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda) p_{a^{(m)}, \tau_1}^{(m)} A_{a^{(m)}, Q, \tau_1}^{(m)}(\lambda); & \text{(method 1)} \\ &= n_{\bar{m}}^2 2^{\frac{N-1}{N} + \delta_{N,1}} p_{a^{(m)}, \tau_1}^{(m)} A_{a^{(m)}, Q, \tau_1}^{(m)'}(\lambda); & \text{(method 2)} \\ &= p_{a^{(m)}, \tau_1}^{(m)} A_{a^{(m)}, Q, \tau_1}^{(m)''}(\lambda); & \text{(method 3)}, \end{aligned} \quad (171)$$

which defines *type-1 quantum measurement functions*,

$$\begin{aligned} A_{a^{(m)}, Q, \tau_1}^{(m)}(\lambda) &\equiv \text{map}[A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)] \\ A_{a^{(m)}, Q, \tau_1}^{(m)'}(\lambda) &\equiv \text{sgn}(\text{map}[A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)]) \\ A_{a^{(m)}, Q, \tau_1}^{(m)''}(\lambda) &\equiv n_{\bar{m}}^2 2^{\frac{N-1}{N} + \delta_{N,1}} \text{sgn}(\text{map}[A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)]), \end{aligned} \quad (172)$$

with *type-1 transmission probability* and scale factor,

$$\begin{aligned} p_{a^{(m)}, \tau_1}^{(m)} &\equiv \frac{|A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)|}{n_{\bar{m}}^2 2^{\frac{N-1}{N} + \delta_{N,1}}} \\ F_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda) &\equiv \frac{n_{\bar{m}}^2 2^{\frac{N-1}{N} + \delta_{N,1}}}{|\text{map}[A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)] + \delta_{\frac{\text{map}[A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda)], 0}|}}, \end{aligned} \quad (173)$$

Here, the method one chooses is up to personal preference. Method 1 lets $A_{a^{(m)}, Q}^{(m)}(\lambda)$ yield actual eigenvalues but requires a λ -dependent scale factor. Method 2 has a constant scale factor and only depends on the *sign* of the eigenvalues, while Method 3 lumps that constant scale factor with the sign of the eigenvalue yielding an *effective eigenvalue* for the quantized value.

Then, for every mode, the *two-type transmission measurement function* can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda) &= F_{k_m}^{(m)}(\lambda) [p_{a^{(m)}, \tau_1}^{(m)} A_{a^{(m)}, Q, \tau_1}^{(m)}(\lambda) + p_{a^{(m)}, \tau_2}^{(m)} A_{a^{(m)}, Q, \tau_2}^{(m)}(\lambda, \tilde{\phi}^{(m)})] \\ &= n_{\bar{m}}^2 2^{\frac{N-1}{N} + \delta_{N,1}} [p_{a^{(m)}, \tau_1}^{(m)} A_{a^{(m)}, Q, \tau_1}^{(m)'}(\lambda) + p_{a^{(m)}, \tau_2}^{(m)} A_{a^{(m)}, Q, \tau_2}^{(m)'}(\lambda, \tilde{\phi}^{(m)})] \\ &= p_{a^{(m)}, \tau_1}^{(m)} A_{a^{(m)}, Q, \tau_1}^{(m)''}(\lambda) + p_{a^{(m)}, \tau_2}^{(m)} A_{a^{(m)}, Q, \tau_2}^{(m)''}(\lambda, \tilde{\phi}^{(m)}), \end{aligned} \quad (174)$$

where $\tilde{\phi}^{(m)}$ is a vector of independent random phase shifts containing a new phase shift for every correlation measurement function for every mode for every particle transmitted, with *type-2 transmission probability*,

$$p_{a^{(m)}, \tau_2}^{(m)} \equiv 1 - p_{a^{(m)}, \tau_1}^{(m)}, \quad (175)$$

with *type-2 quantum measurement functions*,

$$\begin{aligned} A_{a^{(m)}, Q, \tau_2}^{(m)}(\lambda, \tilde{\phi}^{(m)}) &\equiv \text{map}[A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda, \tilde{\phi}^{(m)})] \\ A_{a^{(m)}, Q, \tau_2}^{(m)'}(\lambda, \tilde{\phi}^{(m)}) &\equiv \text{sgn}(\text{map}[A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda, \tilde{\phi}^{(m)})]) \\ A_{a^{(m)}, Q, \tau_2}^{(m)''}(\lambda, \tilde{\phi}^{(m)}) &\equiv n_{\bar{m}}^2 2^{\frac{N-1}{N} + \delta_{N,1}} \text{sgn}(\text{map}[A_{a^{(m)}}^{(m)}(\lambda, \tilde{\phi}^{(m)})]). \end{aligned} \quad (176)$$

Thus, in the two-type transmission model, the mean value of a product of the N measurement functions of (174) expands into a sum over 2^N terms, but the only term that survives the average is the product of all type-1 transmissions which yields agreement with QM as in (155), thus giving us a plausible classical explanation that accounts for everything we observe (including quantization), still using truly local HV measurement functions.

Our ignorance of the magnitude of the classical measurement functions of (171) (possibly via type-1 and type-2 transmission probabilities as in Sec. IV B or above) then leads us to perceive *effectively nonlocal* systems despite their underlying locality.

Now that we have shown that local HV models are indeed possible for all states of two qubits, next we demonstrate it for a variety of multipartite systems.

D. Examples for a Variety of Systems and States

Here we present a wider array of examples to demonstrate the validity of the local HV model in Sec. VII A.

FIG. 8: (color online) Plots of means of product observables in a variety of multipartite systems demonstrating (155). Each pair of dots is computed for an arbitrary state of arbitrary rank, each with N arbitrary local detector vectors, one for each local HV measurement function from (148), 100 trials for each system. The larger dots are the QM result analogous to (160), while smaller dots are the HV result analogous to (163), where each new state and observable is given its own horizontal position in the plot. *The fact that all smaller dots match the bigger dots means that the local HV mean achieves the QM mean in all cases.* Due to the large number of high frequencies and numerical overflow, only the bipartite systems here are computed by integrating the HV averages numerically; for $2 \times 2 \times 2$, symbolic computation to 34 digits of precision was used to verify that the frequencies would achieve the required orthogonality, and then the integrals were computed symbolically by hardcoding, using only the surviving terms, which is justified by the orthogonality test. The remaining systems rely on the derivation of (153) as license to compute the integrals by symbolic hardcoding surviving terms as well.

Figure 8 shows a comparison between local HV and QM mean-value results for product observables of detectors with arbitrary detector-vectors for a variety of mixed states in several multipartite quantum systems. Excellent agreement is achieved in a wide variety of cases, further demonstrating that there always exist local HV models that agree with QM.

E. How Time Evolution Fits into Local HV Models

To understand the role of time evolution in a probabilistic system with a local HV description, we need to review some facts about where it appears in QM in the first place.

1. Quantum expectation values are *not* defined as time averages; they are averages of measurement results over many “identically prepared*” systems [4]. (*Note that this requirement introduces an important caveat that affects time dependence, which we discuss further below in Sec. VII E 2.)
2. For a closed quantum system with Hamiltonian $H \equiv H(t)$, the unitary *time-evolution operator* is

$$U(t) \equiv U(t, t_0) \equiv \tau \left\{ e^{-i \frac{1}{\hbar} \int_{t_0}^t H(t') dt'} \right\}, \quad (177)$$

where $\tau\{\cdot\}$ is the time-ordering operator [24–26]. Note that $U(t)$ is generally *nonlocal*. (Open systems are just reductions of larger closed systems, so for our purposes, it is sufficient to focus on closed systems.)

3. In the *Schrödinger picture*, the time-dependent state evolves as

$$\rho(t) \equiv U(t)\rho(t_0)U^\dagger(t), \quad (178)$$

where ρ is the probability density operator with form $\rho \equiv \sum_j p_j |\psi_j\rangle\langle\psi_j|$, where $\sum_j p_j = 1$ and $p_j \geq 0 \forall j$.

4. For any generally *nonlocal observable* Ω , its mean value can be written as a linear combination of mean values of product observables $\Omega_{\mathbf{k}} \equiv \Omega_{k_1}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes \Omega_{k_N}^{(N)}$, as shown in (137), as

$$\langle\Omega\rangle_\rho = \sum_{\mathbf{k}=0}^{\mathbf{K}} h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \langle\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}\rangle_\rho; \quad h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \equiv \frac{1}{n} \text{tr}(\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \Omega). \quad (179)$$

5. In the *Heisenberg picture*, the operators carry the time dependence as

$$\Omega(t) \equiv U^\dagger(t)\Omega U(t), \quad (180)$$

since cyclic permutation in the trace yields $\langle\Omega\rangle_{\rho(t)} = \text{tr}[\rho(t)\Omega] = \text{tr}[U(t)\rho_0 U^\dagger(t)\Omega] = \text{tr}[\rho_0 U^\dagger(t)\Omega U(t)] \equiv \text{tr}[\rho_0 \Omega(t)] = \langle\Omega(t)\rangle_{\rho_0}$ where $\rho_0 \equiv \rho(t_0)$.

6. Since a product-observable HS-complete basis can expand *any* matrix, then we can use a *constant* product basis to expand $\Omega(t)$ at each time, with all the time-dependence being carried by its *coefficients* as

$$\Omega(t) \equiv \sum_{\mathbf{k}=0}^{\mathbf{K}} h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}(t) \Omega_{\mathbf{k}}; \quad h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}(t) = \frac{1}{n} \text{tr}[\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \Omega(t)]. \quad (181)$$

[Alternatively, by (180), the product basis can carry the time-dependence, while coefficients stay constant, but (181) is more useful to our purpose.]

7. By Facts 5 and 6, the mean value of time-dependent nonlocal observable $\Omega(t)$ is

$$\langle \Omega(t) \rangle_{\rho_0} = \text{tr}[\rho_0 \Omega(t)] = \sum_{\mathbf{k}=0}^{\mathbf{K}} h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}(t) \langle \Omega_{\mathbf{k}} \rangle_{\rho_0}. \quad (182)$$

Thus, Fact 7 establishes that any time-dependent nonlocal observable can be expressed as a linear combination of *constant* mean-values of *product observables* for the system in the *initial state*, with all the time-dependence carried by the time-dependent coefficients $h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}(t)$.

1. Interpretation 1: Time-Dependent Mean Values in Local HV Models

The significance of (182) to local HV theories is that it means that *all observables, including time-dependent nonlocal observables, can be expressed using the local HV principal-direction measurement functions as*

$$\langle \Omega(t) \rangle_{\rho_0} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}=0}^{\mathbf{K}} h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}(t) \langle A_{k_1}^{(1)} \cdots A_{k_N}^{(N)} \rangle_L, \quad (183)$$

where $\langle A_{k_1}^{(1)} \cdots A_{k_N}^{(N)} \rangle_L \equiv \frac{1}{L} \int_0^L A_{k_1}^{(1)}(\lambda) \cdots A_{k_N}^{(N)}(\lambda) d\lambda$ [using the simplified mean for λ -periodic functions from the text after (154)], with time-dependent coefficients

$$h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}(t) \equiv \frac{1}{n} \text{tr}[\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \Omega(t)] = \frac{1}{n} \text{tr}[\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger U^\dagger(t) \Omega U(t)]. \quad (184)$$

Therefore, since any nonlocal time-dependent observable has its mean expressible as (183), the initial state still serves as something that represents initial synchronizations in a local creation of the system that are *not* changed over time, thus maintaining the locality of the local HV model. Then, any true nonlocality comes from either or both Ω and/or $U(t)$, as seen in (183) and (184). (We have already shown that means of product observables can *seem* nonlocal as with Bell's example yielding $-\cos(\theta_{a,b})$, but that such nonlocality can be a *mirage* arising from a time average washing out crucial cross terms as in Sec. IV A, but here Ω itself can be nonlocal.)

However, note that the local HV measurement functions are still all we need to predict the instantaneous results for the whole system – any request for the results for a nonlocal operator is simply a predictable linear combination of the means of local product functions.

The result in (183) suggests that we could define a time-and- λ -dependent general measurement function as

$$A(t, \lambda) \equiv \sum_{\mathbf{k}=0}^{\mathbf{K}} h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}(t) A_{k_1}^{(1)}(\lambda) \cdots A_{k_N}^{(N)}(\lambda), \quad (185)$$

and then the mean of any general observable would be

$$\langle \Omega(t) \rangle_{\rho_0} = \langle A(t, \lambda) \rangle_L. \quad (186)$$

In this perspective, $A(t, \lambda)$ is generally a nonlocal measurement function, but it is still a linear combination of *local* measurement functions, and its nonlocality poses no problem because the observable it represents *is* nonlocal.

However, an interesting dilemma appears if we consider what would happen *if the HV were time itself* (or a function of time). In that case, the HV expectation values become time averages, and we get a seeming conceptual contradiction of having time-dependent time averages.

Indeed, since one of the main motivations of HV theories is to find some deterministic functions to predict the measurement results that QM is missing, any HV model would need to involve time dependence in some form.

One possible solution to this conundrum is to specify that perhaps the expectation values $\langle A_{k_1}^{(1)} \cdots A_{k_N}^{(N)} \rangle_L$ in (183) are “microscopic time averages” that converge over some time interval that’s longer than the fundamental period T of the HV functions but still very brief in time (implying that T is very small), and that the general time dependence of $\langle \Omega(t) \rangle_{\rho_0}$ is effectively a different time variable, changing relatively slowly compared to the measurement functions, to be averaged on a much larger scale, thereby giving a natural explanation to (183) with $\lambda = t'$ up to the fundamental period $L = T$.

However, there is a much more self-consistent and satisfying way to resolve this conundrum that actually may fix a deeper problem of QM as well, as we discuss next.

2. Interpretation 2: Revisiting the Concept of Identical Preparation Allows More Consistent Definition of Mean Values in QM and Fits Better with Local HV Models

Alternatively, a much simpler way to view time evolution is to acknowledge that if the system is truly changing over time, then *if we allow measurements at different times within some measurement time window, we are not actually preparing the trial systems in identical ways.*

As a reminder of why measurements typically need to happen over a time window, recall that for absorptive-projective filtration, a beam in state $|\psi(t)\rangle$ entering a detector can be thought of as first passing through a beam splitter with vacuum in its auxiliary input, and then tracing over the auxiliary output yields a *quantum mixture* of the projected state with the vacuum state, such as $\rho'(t) = p|0\rangle\langle 0| + (1-p)|\psi(t)\rangle\langle\psi(t)|$ [27]. The vacuum outcome is then responsible for why we cannot anticipate *when* a detection will happen, which necessitates

a detection time window and the inability to precisely control the detection time after initial state preparation.

To fix this conceptual flaw in identical state preparation, we could simply return to the Schrödinger picture, and specify that *to achieve truly identically-prepared quantum systems, we must agree to only accept measurements at a certain time after the initial preparation* (not merely within some interval), thus postselecting the results for a state prepared at a particular time t_* after the preparation process is initialized. (Although this definitely increases the number of trials one must perform for a valid measurement to happen at t_* , this synchronization is a necessary part of being able to claim that the system was “identically prepared.”)

Then, since the resulting state is a *constant state* in terms of the model because it is $\rho(t_*)$ at the particular time t_* , the method in Sec. VII A shows that *we can always find a local HV model for such a system* (which is to say, *all quantum systems*), and (183) shows that *any nonlocal observable can be expressed as a linear combination of means of product observables still employing the local HV measurement functions as*

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Omega \rangle_{\rho(t_*)} &= \sum_{\mathbf{k}=0}^{\mathbf{K}} h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \langle \Omega_{k_1}^{(1)} \otimes \cdots \otimes \Omega_{k_N}^{(N)} \rangle_{\rho(t_*)} \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{k}=0}^{\mathbf{K}} h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \langle A_{k_1}^{(1)} \cdots A_{k_N}^{(N)} \rangle_T, \end{aligned} \quad (187)$$

with *constant coefficients*

$$h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \equiv \frac{1}{n} \text{tr}(\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \Omega), \quad (188)$$

where *the time t_* that defines when acceptable measurements occur after initial setup defines the effective initial preparation state as $\rho_0 \equiv \rho(t_*)$* . The HV product means $\langle A_{k_1}^{(1)} \cdots A_{k_N}^{(N)} \rangle_T$ can then still be viewed as time averages in the sense that experimentally there will always be some spread of times Δt_* about t_* that cannot be avoided, and if $T \ll \Delta t_*$, the time average will be a natural consequence of Δt_* . Note that this also requires that $U(t)$ does not vary appreciably over the experimental tolerance of Δt_* about t_* , so that the concept of identical preparation still holds, while the measurement functions would vary much more rapidly, yet their initial phase offsets would still be determined by the constant $\rho(t_*)$.

Furthermore, this would resolve the conceptual conundrum of expectation values in QM by allowing them to be viewed as time averages while *still also being interpreted as mean values over many identically prepared systems*.

This is possible because the state of a truly identically prepared system is the same constant state $\rho(t_*)$ as above, and while the lack of outcome prediction of QM forces us to use many such identically prepared systems to get estimators of a mean value, the mean value itself is then free to be interpreted as a time average of some underlying dynamical variable like a hidden variable.

Then, to explain why the mean values might change over time (if indeed they still do when we use this refined definition of identical preparation), we could simply say

that it is because the system itself is changing (such as if it is open), and in this way, at each new time, there is a different instantaneous state of the system, each having its own local HV model.

Then, since each “instant” in time always admits a local HV model, any time dependence can always be resolved into a time-dependent local HV model.

The Heisenberg version of this would be expressed as

$$\langle \Omega(t_*) \rangle_{\rho_0} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}=0}^{\mathbf{K}} h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}(t_*) \langle A_{k_1}^{(1)} \cdots A_{k_N}^{(N)} \rangle_T, \quad (189)$$

still with constant coefficients

$$h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}(t_*) \equiv \frac{1}{n} \text{tr}[\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \Omega(t_*)] = \frac{1}{n} \text{tr}[\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger U^\dagger(t_*) \Omega U(t_*)], \quad (190)$$

only now it is the *observable* that is identically prepared (since that is what varies in the Heisenberg picture), and again this requires that $U(t)$ does not change appreciably over Δt_* , and here, the original $\rho_0 \equiv \rho(0)$ determines the initial phases in the measurement functions, and the experimental tolerance Δt_* is still long compared to T so that the measurement functions still get time averaged, while $h_{\Omega_{\mathbf{k}}}(t_*)$ is essentially constant.

In terms of locality, (189) is preferable to (187), because the time-averaged measurement functions in (189) have their phases determined by the true initial state $\rho_0 \equiv \rho(0)$, which allows for the particles to achieve their synchronizations from some local creation event before flying apart.

Note that QM *already does use time averages for expectation values* in certain cases. For example, the Bloch-vector components of a single-qubit polarization state are measured from *time averages* of squares of the electric field via intensities (nor is this limited to one qubit).

Thus, regardless of any physical interpretation of the hidden variable (whether it is time or something else), we have now shown that it is always possible to model any observable using a truly local HV theory in a way that fully agrees with QM.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have successfully disproven the Bell inequality and all Bell-type inequalities, and have given an explicit example of a local HV model that correctly agrees with quantum mechanics (and thus the physical results) for a system in a maximally entangled state. The paper culminates by proving that local HV models are possible for all observables of all multipartite discrete systems in all states, giving general formulas for explicit constructions of local HV models in all cases.

Before discussing our results, we briefly summarize them here as both a reminder and a **Reader’s Guide**:

III A. We show that Bell omitted lone spin averages implicit in his model, which is part of why his “local” HV product average $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ is not compatible with the QM expectation value, which is why violations of his inequality can occur.

- III B.** We see that fixing Bell’s omission leads to the local HV product average $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ yielding the QM result, but causes nonlocal probabilities. So his “inequality” would be an *inviolable equality*, but he would still have concluded that only nonlocal HVs were possible for his maximally entangled state. We call this an *effectively nonlocal* HV model because, as we show in Sec. IV C, it can arise from a *local* HV model where we are ignorant of some of its features.
- IV A.** We show that there exist truly local measurement functions and a PDF for a *local* HV model that agrees with QM for Bell’s system.
- IV B.** We suggest a way to include quantization that proves there exists a quantized local HV model that agrees with QM for this system, fully disproving Bell by example.
- IV C.** We show that the nonquantized local HV model with ignorance of spin-component magnitudes leads to the same effectively nonlocal HV model that Bell would have found if he had included the lone spin-component averages as in Sec. III B.
- V A.** Shows that any Bell-type inequality from the *local* HV model can never be violated.
- V B.** Shows that any Bell-type inequality in the effectively nonlocal HV model can never be violated.
- V C.** Shows that any CHSH-type inequalities from either the effectively nonlocal or the local HV model can never be violated.
- VI.** Develops a method to convert any quantum system to an effectively nonlocal HV model that is compatible with an underlying *local* HV model in the same way as the two examples from Sec. IV.
- VII.** Presents a method to get a *truly local HV model for all discrete quantum systems*, fully disproving Bell’s claims for all such systems.

Now we are ready to discuss our results in greater depth.

In Sec. III, we proved that Bell’s original local HV model is *incomplete* because it does not account for the lone spin-component averages, and if he had included those, the Bell “inequality” would actually be an *equality* and furthermore, it could never be violated.

As shown in Sec. III B, including the lone spin-component averages as constraints, the four main physical constraints (normalization, spin-component product average, and both lone spin-component averages) lead to a discrete system of equations with a specific set of solutions for the probabilities. This means that if Bell’s “local” HV model had included them, its prediction for the spin-component product average $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ would be *exactly equal* to the quantum-mechanical (and physical) result of $-c_{\theta_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}}}$; i.e. his model would have already given the correct answer exactly. Then, the tightest inequality possible is simply equality to the physical result, so there can never be any Bell-inequality violations when it is properly derived.

However, Sec. III B also showed that the discrete probabilities that emerged in that solution are *nonlocal* since they depend on the relative detector angle through $c_{\theta_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}}}$. This would then *seem* to be an alternative way to prove Bell’s thesis – that perhaps since the solution to the “local” HV system is itself *nonlocal*, maybe that proves that a local HV model just is not possible...

But in Sec. IV, we gave an explicit example that showed that *the “nonlocality” of the corrected Bell model is merely a side-effect of perception due to assuming that spins are inherently quantized*. That is, by imposing quantization on the spin components from the start, Bell infected his intended local HV model with nonlocality, even if only the *effective* kind. The solution, as we showed in Sec. IV is to not initially make quantum assumptions by instead using full local realism to construct a truly classical model from the start. We did this by proposing *classical measurement functions* $A_C(\mathbf{a}, t)$ and $B_C(\mathbf{b}, t)$ that have continuous nonquantized magnitudes, and we used time t as the “hidden” variable. The *locality* of our measurement functions comes from the fact that *each only depends on its own local detector vector*, and the uniform PDF of t is compatible with locality as well.

Section IV A showed that *our truly local HV model correctly predicted all of the results of the Bohm-Aharonov-Bell system*, while also implicitly including possible quantum measurement functions as the two-case sign of the classical measurement functions, and *thereby giving deterministic predictions for the results of all quantum measurements for this example as functions of time*. (Note that we do not claim this model to be the description of physical reality, but rather the fact that such a local HV model agreeing with QM is possible at all is positive proof that Bell’s conclusion was wrong, and therefore local HV models cannot be ruled out for the reasons he claimed, and EPR has not yet been disproven.)

Section IV B gave a possible classical physical motivation for why we might not have access to the spin-component magnitudes, and how that might lead to the quantum measurement functions being the only measurable results. This is an even more persuasive counterexample to Bell’s claim because it accounts for the physical fact of quantization while maintaining locality and still achieving full agreement with QM.

Then, Sec. IV C showed that if we were ignorant of spin-component magnitudes in the truly local HV model, that would naturally lead us to *perceive* the system as being “nonlocal,” yielding the same exact solution that Bell would have gotten if he had included the lone spin-component averages. Since this result came from a fundamentally *local* HV model, we call it an *effectively nonlocal* HV model since the nonlocality is just a side-effect of our lack of information about the spin-component magnitudes, even though they are actually there.

Section V then took a deeper look at rederiving the Bell inequality. In Sec. V A we showed that our local HV model leads to an inequality that is always true for all physical data. In Sec. V B, we showed that the effectively

nonlocal HV model that Bell should have gotten if he had included lone spin-component averages also leads to an *equality* that can never be violated because it is the correct answer. We also found inequalities, but they are looser, so they can never be violated either.

In Sec. V C we examined the CHSH inequality, and showed that since it depends on Bell’s mean-value function $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$, it inherits the same flaw and is therefore not a valid inequality. When correcting their model by including the missing lone spin-component averages, $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ again gives the physically correct result already in the model, and in that case the *corrected* CHSH “inequality” becomes an *equality*, and it cannot be violated because it is the correct physical value. We also showed that if we use our truly local HV model, its resulting inequality is also always satisfied by all physical results, which we demonstrated by using the most extreme example and showing that it gives equality in that case.

Overall, what Sec. IV and Sec. V show is that *it is really Bell’s omission of the nonquantized spin-component magnitudes that causes his inequality to be too tight*. We have shown multiple ways that these classical components can be included that are compatible with QM, and it is this possibility that Bell’s model was really missing.

The reason our effectively nonlocal model does not also lead to the original Bell inequality is because that model requires *probabilities that depend on relative detector angle $\theta_{a,b}$* (which is what makes it nonlocal), but that dependence fundamentally changes how the derivation of a Bell-type inequality can proceed [Bell’s PDF $\rho(\lambda)$ only depended on λ , which he would have seen was not consistent with his model if he had included the lone spin averages]. For our local HV models, the PDF is *local* (because it is an independent constant), but *it is the spin-component magnitudes’ dependence on local detector angles that generally changes the course of a Bell-type inequality derivation* (which is true whether we model it with nonquantized spin-component magnitudes or with quantization via two-type transmission which includes the same quantities as local transmission probabilities).

Then, in Sec. VI we showed that for discrete systems, all of quantum mechanics can be converted to a form that is analogous to the effectively nonlocal HV model that Bell would have gotten or equivalently, the effectively nonlocal HV model we got by assuming observer ignorance of the spin-component magnitudes in our local HV model. In Sec. VI D we showed how to express any observable in terms of a classical average with a single classical discrete probability distribution, strengthening the idea that a classical description of QM is possible.

Finally, in Sec. VII, we gave a general explicit construction for local HV models capable of handling any observable for any multipartite discrete system in any state, pure or mixed. Specifically, we showed how to construct truly *local* measurement functions where the locality comes from their dependence only on local detector parameters for each mode, and any correlations of the system are modeled as constants determined by

initial conditions; i.e. at the time of creation of the joint system, any initial synchronization between parts of the system happens locally and leaves its mark upon the different parts as a correlation between them, evident in their related motions as they fly apart. (In other words, even though causation does not imply correlation, it is equally true that causation *can* cause correlation, such as through initially-local synchronization.)

Since we have shown that all discrete quantum systems permit a *local* HV model that is fully compatible with quantum mechanics, this is very strong evidence that we cannot use Bell’s argument to rule out the possibility of local hidden variables.

Whether or not such local HV models correspond to *physical reality* is another matter. It may be that there are many different dynamical local HV models that *mathematically work* for a given system, but that do not necessarily predict the particular evolution of the “actual” hidden variable if it exists. Or it may just be a mathematical *isomorphism* to quantum mechanics – our world may indeed be truly quantum-mechanical, and the ability to model it with local HVs may be simply a mathematical fact, with no direct physical repercussions. (In that case, the dynamic information about the future of particular measurement results would be a nonphysical artefact similar to global phase.)

A consequence of the possibility of multiple different local HV models possibly being mathematically compatible to a given system is that *even if one local HV model is experimentally verified not to apply, that does not necessarily mean that some other local HV model does not apply instead*.

This means that, just as we proved that properly-derived Bell inequalities cannot be violated and therefore cannot be used as tests of local HV viability, *an experiment that rules out a particular local HV model does not necessarily rule out all of them*.

Most importantly, we have proven that all Bell-type inequalities, when properly derived, can never be violated, and therefore at least in principle, *local hidden variables are compatible with quantum mechanics, and also with whatever experimental results are described by quantum mechanics, by the Correspondance Principle*.

While it is likely that our particular examples of local HV models are not the literal truth, the mere fact that they are possible at all shows the EPR was not wrong to suggest that quantum mechanics may be incomplete. At the very least, we must now accept that Bell’s and others’ claim that “local HV theories are not compatible with QM” is not a valid claim after all.

The most difficult part of this to accept for the physics community will be the fact that “Bell violations” have been experimentally confirmed. But since we have shown that the Bell inequality was not properly derived, these experiments have all been putting their perfectly good data into what is effectively a *nonsense inequality* that does not properly represent a true local HV model. As we have shown, all properly derived Bell inequalities cannot

be violated. Therefore, *all of the data from those same experiments, when put into properly derived Bell inequalities, will only confirm that local HV models are possible.* Therefore all of that experimental evidence was wrongly interpreted due to the use of a wrongly-derived inequality, and ironically *that same data will actually vindicate EPR when used in the proper inequalities.* (That is, it will not prove that EPR was correct, but rather it proves that EPR’s concept has not yet been disproven after all, since local HV models are compatible with quantum mechanics’s description of physical results.)

Indeed, one of the strange features of Bell’s original inequality is that the transition of when violations start to happen does not seem to be strongly linked to non-local correlation such as entanglement, as shown by the existence of Werner states [28], which include entangled states that do *not* violate Bell’s inequality (making it relatively useless as an entanglement measure). We now see a likely reason for this arbitrary cutoff of Bell inequality violations; Bell’s inequality itself has no meaning since it has no connection to reality, quantum mechanics, or local hidden-variable theories – that is why the violations appear to happen for an arbitrary amount of entanglement.

As mentioned, there may be more than one compatible local HV model for a given system, and not all might agree with reality about which measurement results happen at exact time, and in fact, none of them *need* to be correct deterministically to agree with QM, because QM is not deterministic in regard to measurements.

However, regardless of whether our local HV models are physically true or not, *we can actually use them to construct a classical physical system that, when observed, will exhibit the same behavior as a quantum system in a maximally entangled state* (or any other state for that matter). This opens the door to an entire new subject area of technological possibilities.

Therefore, here we propose that it is possible to build artificial local HV systems to achieve things like *hidden-variable teleporters* that achieve quantum teleportation [27, 29–31] and *hidden-variable computers* that act like quantum computers [32, 33] by performing actual quantum algorithms [34–39]. This is possible because we have proven that local HV models agree with QM, regardless of whether reality actually “runs” on HVs. All we have to do is build or simulate the classical system whose local HV model corresponds to the desired QM system. Most significantly, the time-dependence of the classical measurement functions in such a theory might let us do things we simply cannot do in quantum mechanics, such as extract particular answers from a superposition state resulting from a quantum computation, simply by waiting for the time at which that outcome yields a measurement as predicted by our local HV model.

For HV teleportation, while we still expect the light-speed limit to be obeyed, there may be a practical improvement. For example, the secret state to be teleported would be essentially encoded in the initial phase shifts of its measurement functions, and the receiver (and usually

the sender) does not know them ahead of time. But because they both can *predict* the results of the sender’s Bell measurement, the receiver knows exactly what corrective local unitary to apply to obtain the proper secret state at a given time. Thus the state would be transmitted instantly, but the information would still take time to extract if the receiver wanted to read the secret. Indeed, a valid extraction of the information would take an infinite number of measurements to obtain the *perfect* message (in theory) (even if using a pre-agreed basis for one-shot measurements, since there is uncertainty in any measurement), so Special Relativity (SR) would not be violated in principle. In practice, it might be possible to obtain the correct message with excellent certainty in a time shorter than a classical signal could send it, all without violating SR. However, it may be that the secret state’s unknown initial conditions might lead to both parties being uncertain of the Bell measurement, restoring the need to send the results with a light-speed limit.

These possibilities are so extensive that we cannot possibly explore them all here in the present paper, and we have not yet investigated them in depth. Therefore these are excellent topics for further research.

Our proof of the compatibility between local HVs and QM did not require the use of other alternative theories such as *pilot-wave theory* [40–44] (which is nonlocal), but such theories might benefit from this new result, which might make for another interesting topic of research.

Regarding *loopholes* such as [45–53], they actually cannot affect our results. Loopholes are experimental ways in which QM might actually be shown to be a mirage of perception hiding an underlying local classical reality despite the experimental violations of Bell’s original inequality. For instance, by showing that with large-enough sample sizes the statistics look completely different from what QM predicts, or that by separating the detectors enough in space, some light-speed-communication between the particles can fail to arrive in time to account for last-minute changes in detector angle. But none of that matters here because we have found a family of local HV models that already agrees with QM, thereby disproving Bell’s claim by example for all discrete quantum systems, and his claim was merely about the compatibility of QM with local HVs. Furthermore, since our corrected Bell inequalities can never be violated, no valid experimental tests can disagree with them, even if we use data that produced violations of Bell’s original inequality.

In closing, we have disproven Bell’s disproof of local hidden-variable theories, and presented an explicit local hidden-variable example leading to corrected Bell inequalities that can never be violated by physical results. We have also presented general explicit constructions of local HV models in all multipartite discrete systems, for all observables and all states, showing that quantum mechanics is indeed compatible with local hidden-variable theories. Therefore, EPR is vindicated in their hypothesis that a more-complete version of physics than quantum mechanics is possible, at least in principle.

Appendix A: The Cosine Product Identity

The identity $c_{\theta_1} c_{\theta_2} = \frac{1}{2}(c_{\theta_1+\theta_2} + c_{\theta_1-\theta_2})$ generalizes as

$$\prod_{m=1}^N c_{\theta_m} = \frac{1}{2^{N-1}} \sum_{a=1}^{2^{N-1}} c_{\sum_{b=1}^N \sigma_{a,b} \theta_b}, \quad (\text{A1})$$

where $c_{\theta} \equiv \cos(\theta)$ and $\sigma_{a,b} \equiv 3 - 2(\mathbf{a}_a^{\{N,\mathbf{n}\}})_b$ is a function of the *inverse indicial register function* [19],

$$\mathbf{a}_a^{\{N,\mathbf{n}\}} = (a_1, \dots, a_N); \begin{cases} a_m = \text{floor}(\frac{v_{m-1}-1}{d_m}) + 1 \\ v_m = v_{m-1} - (a_m - 1)d_m \end{cases} \quad (\text{A2})$$

for $m \in 1, \dots, N$, where $\mathbf{n} \equiv (n_1, \dots, n_N) = (2, \dots, 2)$ here, $v_0 \equiv a$, $d_m \equiv \prod_{q=m+1}^N n_q$, and $a \in 1, \dots, \prod_{q=1}^N n_q$.

Moving the factor of 2^{N-1} to the left in (A1) and splitting it into N factors of $2^{(N-1)/N}$ is why each cosine in (151) has an amplitude of $2^{(N-1)/N}$. The fact that (A1) always has one term with an all-plus argument of angles is why we specify all frequencies must sum to 0 in (152); so that exactly *one* term in (A1) is *constant* to survive the time average. Then (153) is simply an algorithm to ensure that only *one* term survives the time average in every N -factor product $A_{k_1}^{(1)} \cdots A_{k_N}^{(N)}$; the term whose factors correspond to the \mathbf{k} of the product observable.

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- [1] A. Einstein, B. Podolsky, and N. Rosen, Phys. Rev. **47**, 777 (1935).
- [2] D. Bohm and Y. Aharonov, Phys. Rev. **108**, 1070 (1957).
- [3] J. S. Bell, Physics **1**, 195 (1964).
- [4] D. J. Griffiths, *Introduction to Quantum Mechanics*, 2nd ed. (Pearson Education, Inc., 2005) p. 423.
- [5] M. Genovese, Physics Reports **413**, 319 (2005).
- [6] N. Harrigan and R. W. Spekkens, Found. Phys. **40**, 125 (2010).
- [7] E. Hecht, *Optics*, 4th ed. (Pearson Education, Inc., 2002) p. 49.
- [8] J. F. Clauser, M. A. Horne, A. Shimony, and R. A. Holt, Phys. Rev. Lett. **23**, 880 (1969).
- [9] A. Aspect, P. Grangier, and G. Roger, Phys. Rev. Lett. **49**, 91 (1982).
- [10] A. Aspect, J. Dalibard, and G. Roger, Phys. Rev. Lett. **49**, 1804 (1982).
- [11] S. Stenholm and K.-A. Suominen, *Quantum Approach to Informatics* (John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2005) p. 47.
- [12] C. C. Gerry and P. L. Knight, *Introductory Quantum Optics* (Cambridge University Press, 2005) p. 230.
- [13] D. F. V. James, P. G. Kwiat, W. J. Munro, and A. G. White, Phys. Rev. A **64**, 052312 (2001).
- [14] S. R. Hedemann, *Hyperspherical Bloch Vectors with Applications to Entanglement and Quantum State Tomography*, Ph.D. thesis, Stevens Institute of Technology (2014).
- [15] F. Bloch, Phys. Rev. **70**, 460 (1946).
- [16] G. G. Stokes, Trans. Cambridge Philos. Soc. **9**, 399 (1852).
- [17] J. von Neumann, Göttinger Nachrichten, **1**, 245 (1927).
- [18] F. T. Hioe and J. H. Eberly, Phys. Rev. Lett. **47**, 838 (1981).
- [19] S. R. Hedemann, Quantum Inf. Process. **19**, 189 (2020), arXiv:2001.03453.
- [20] L. Schläfli, J. H. Graf, ed., 1901 (1852 orig.).
- [21] S. R. Hedemann, arXiv preprint (2013), arXiv:1303.5904.
- [22] Y. Ne'eman, Nucl. Phys. **26**, 222 (1961).
- [23] M. Gell-Mann, Phys. Rev. **125**, 1067 (1962).
- [24] J. J. Sakurai, *Modern Quantum Mechanics* (Addison-Wesley Publishing Company, 1994) p. 73, rev. Ed., S. F. Tuan, Ed.
- [25] F. J. Dyson, Phys. Rev. **75**, 1736 (1949).
- [26] M. Suzuki, Proc. Japan Acad. **69B**, 161 (1993).
- [27] S. R. Hedemann, arXiv preprint (2016), arXiv:1605.09233.
- [28] R. F. Werner, Phys. Rev. A **40**, 4277 (1989).
- [29] C. H. Bennett, G. Brassard, C. Crépeau, R. Jozsa, A. Peres, and W. K. Wootters, Phys. Rev. Lett. **70**, 1895 (1993).
- [30] D. Bouwmeester, J. W. Pan, K. Mattle, M. Eibl, H. Weinfurter, and A. Zeilinger, Nature **390**, 575 (1997).
- [31] D. Bouwmeester, J. W. Pan, K. Mattle, M. Eibl, H. Weinfurter, and A. Zeilinger, Phil. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. A **356**, 1733 (1998).
- [32] R. P. Feynman, Found. Phys. **16**, 507 (1986).
- [33] D. P. DiVincenzo, Fortschritte der Physik **48**, 771 (2000).
- [34] P. W. Shor, Proc. 35th Annual Symposium on Fundamentals of Comput. Science, 124 (1994).
- [35] P. W. Shor, SIAM J. Sci. Statist. Comput. **26**, 1484 (1997).
- [36] L. K. Grover, Proc. 28th Annual ACM Symposium on the Theory of Computing, 212 (1996).
- [37] D. Deutsch, Proc. R. Soc. Lond. A **400**, 97 (1985).
- [38] D. Deutsch and R. Jozsa, Proc. R. Soc. Lond. A **439**, 553 (1992).
- [39] R. Cleve, A. Ekert, C. Macchiavello, and M. Mosca, Proc. R. Soc. Lond. A **454**, 339 (1998).
- [40] L. de Broglie, Journal de Physique et le Radium **8**, 225 (1927).
- [41] D. Bohm, Phys. Rev. **85**, 166 (1952).
- [42] D. Bohm, Phys. Rev. **85**, 180 (1952).
- [43] A. Valentini, *On the Pilot-Wave Theory of Classical, Quantum and Subquantum Physics*, Ph.D. thesis (1992), <https://iris.sissa.it/handle/20.500.11767/4334>.
- [44] W. Struyve, Rept. Prog. Phys. **73**, 106001 (2010).
- [45] E. Santos, Phys. Rev. A **46**, 3646 (1992).
- [46] G. Weihs, T. Jennewein, C. Simon, H. Weinfurter, and A. Zeilinger, Phys. Rev. Lett. **81**, 5039 (1998).
- [47] N. Gisin and B. Gisin, Phys. Lett. A **260**, 323 (1999).
- [48] K. Hess and W. Philipp, Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. **98**, 14224 (2001).
- [49] R. D. Gill, G. Weihs, A. Zeilinger, and M. Żukowski, Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. **99**, 14632 (2002).
- [50] J. Barrett, D. Collins, L. Hardy, A. Kent, and S. Popescu, Phys. Rev. A **66**, 042111 (2002).
- [51] J.-Å. Larsson, J. Phys. A: Math. Theor. **47**, 424003 (2014).
- [52] T. M. Nieuwenhuizen and M. Kupczynski, Found. Phys. **47**, 316 (2017).
- [53] M. Czachor, Acta Physica Polonica A **139**, 70 (2021).